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Executive Summary

This deliverable, D3.2 – U2Demo Standardization, Cybersecurity, and Data Privacy, defines the technical, semantic, and security foundations required for the development and deployment of the U2Demo platform, an open-source peer-to-peer (P2P) energy sharing and flexibility management solution for diverse Energy Community (EC) contexts. It is produced under Task T3.2 – Standards, Interoperability, and Cybersecurity, which ensures that the platform is designed to be interoperable, secure, standards-aligned, and replicable across different regulatory and technical environments in the European Union (EU).

The work begins with a comprehensive consortium-wide questionnaire to assess the current status of the adoption of interoperability standards, communication protocols, data models, cybersecurity measures, and data privacy practices. The analysis reveals significant heterogeneity: while some partners are already aligned with open standards such as Smart Applications REFERENCE (SAREF) [1], [2], Smart Energy Aware Systems (SEAS) [3], and Open Automated Demand Response (OPENADR) [4], [5], others rely on proprietary protocols, ad-hoc data formats, and minimal security controls. This diversity highlights the need for a harmonized semantic and technical integration framework.

To address this, the deliverable develops a modular, FAIR-compliant (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) ontology following a six-step agile methodology adapted from Agile Interaction Model based ontology development Methodology (AIME) [6]. The ontology reuses and aligns with existing European standards and ontologies (SAREF, SEAS, ENERSHARE [7]) and introduces U2Demo-specific modules to cover gaps in areas like internal community pricing, flexibility scheduling, EC governance roles, and domain-specific event taxonomies. A set of eleven interoperable core modules (System, Player, Market, Forecast, TimeSeries, Schedule, Device, Building, Event, Price, and Properties) has been defined to enable a consistent, machine-readable representation of data across heterogeneous systems.

Beyond semantic alignment, interoperability is also addressed at the architectural level, including integration scenarios with Simpl Middleware [8] to enable secure, contract-based data exchange across pilot systems. It provides detailed Application Programming Interface (API) requirements and supported data exchange formats, illustrated with the Energy Web (EW) Digital Spine Client as a reference implementation. This includes both RESTful and WebSocket (WSS) APIs, covering modules such as authentication, user and key management, enterprise credential handling, client gateway configuration, topic and channel management, address book services, and secure messaging. Supported formats include JSON objects (JSD-7 specification) and file-based formats such as JSON, Comma-separated values (CSV), Table-separated values (TSV), and eXtensible Markup Language (XML). Together, these specifications and authentication methods (Open Authorization Protocol OAuth2, Mutual Transport Layer Security mTLS) ensure secure, standardised, and consistent data sharing across the U2Demo ecosystem.

A multi-layered cybersecurity and data privacy framework has been established, grounded in internationally recognized standards (International Organization for Standardization/International Electrotechnical Commission (ISO/IEC) 27001 [9], IEC 62443 [10], [11], National Institute of Standards and Technology Interagency Reports (NISTIR) 7628 [12]) and fully aligned with EU regulatory requirements (General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR [13], Network and Information Systems 2 Directive - NIS 2 [14], and the forthcoming Network Code on Cybersecurity [15]). The framework introduces strong authentication (Public key infrastructure - PKI, Multi-factor authentication - MFA), encryption in transit and at rest (Transport Layer Security TLS 1.3 [16], Advanced Encryption Standard AES-256[17]), granular access control (Role-based access control - RBAC, Attribute-based access control - ABAC),

secure logging and auditing, and privacy-by-design principles. Special attention is given to risks inherent in P2P environments, such as rogue node injection, data manipulation, and unauthorized control. Countermeasures include device attestation, anomaly detection, and secure onboarding protocols, ensuring robust protection of operational and personal data.

The deliverable concludes that interoperability and cybersecurity must be developed together to ensure trust, resilience, and scalability. The next steps focus on formalizing the ontology in machine-readable formats, developing API, data models and their specifications (D3.4), potentially creating protocol adapters for proprietary systems, implementing the security baseline across all partners, and validating interoperability and security in pilot environments.

By combining semantic standardization, secure architecture, and alignment with the frameworks, previously developed in European projects, this deliverable ensures that the U2Demo platform is positioned as a robust, trustworthy, and replicable solution for energy communities, capable of scaling across different technical and regulatory landscapes in Europe.

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Acronyms

ABAC	Attribute-based access control
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
AIME	Agile Interaction Model based ontology development Methodology
API	Application Programming Interface
BACS	Building Automation and Control Systems
BEM	Block Element Modifier
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BO	Business Object
BUC	Business Use Case
CIM	Common Information Model
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSV	Comma-separated values
DA	Day-Ahead
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DID	Decentralized Identifier
DS	Data Space
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	Energy Community
EMS	Energy Management Systems
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
EW	Energy Web
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEMS	Grid Energy Management System
HBES	Home and Building Electronic Systems
HEMS	Home Energy Management System
HP	Heat Pump
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
MFA	Multi-factor authentication
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
mTLS	Mutual Transport Layer Security
NCCS	Network Code on Cybersecurity
NIS 2	Network and Information Systems 2 Directive
NISTIR	National Institute of Standards and Technology Interagency Reports
OAuth2	Open Authorization Protocol
OCPI	Open Charge Point Interface
OCPP	Open Charge Point Protocol
OPENADR	Open Automated Demand Response
OWL	Web Ontology Language
P2P	peer-to-peer
PKI	Public key infrastructure
PV	Photovoltaic
RBAC	Role-based access control
RDF/S	Resource Description Framework Schema
REST	Representational State Transfer
RM	Resource Manager

SAREF	Smart Applications REFerence
SEAS	Smart Energy Aware Systems
sFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SMPC	Secure Multi-Party Computation
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TSO	Transmission System Operator
TSV	Tab-separated values
TTL	Terse Triple Language
UC	Use Case
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope and Objectives

The U2Demo project, “Use of Open-Source P2P Energy Sharing Platforms for Energy Democratization” is a Horizon Europe initiative that aims to demonstrate innovative peer-to-peer (P2P) energy sharing models and local flexibility markets across diverse Energy Community (EC) contexts in Portugal, Italy, Belgium, and the Netherlands. By combining open-source digital platforms, interoperable semantic models, and advanced cybersecurity frameworks, U2Demo seeks to empower citizens, prosumers, and community managers to actively participate in local energy transactions, improve transparency in energy flows, and strengthen trust among participants.

A key challenge, identified based on the detailed questionnaire-based assessment of consortium partners, is the heterogeneity of practices across partners regarding interoperability, standards adoption, data exchange protocols, cybersecurity measures, and data protection. While some actors are already aligned with established European standards and ontologies, others rely on proprietary or fragmented approaches, which creates barriers for harmonization and replication.

This deliverable, **D3.2 - “U2Demo Standardization, Cybersecurity, and Data Privacy”**, is produced under Task T3.2 – “Standards, Interoperability, and Cybersecurity” and responds to this challenge by laying the technical, semantic, and security foundations that will support the development of the U2Demo platform. Its objective is not only to highlight the gaps in the current landscape but also to define a common approach that ensures interoperability, resilience, and trustworthiness across diverse pilot contexts.

In doing so, the deliverable provides the basis for U2Demo to operate as a scalable and reliable P2P solution, aligned with European regulatory and technical requirements, and capable of supporting the EU’s broader objectives for energy democratization and digitalization.

1.2 Structure

The deliverable is organized into six main parts:

- **Section 1 – Introduction**
Presents the scope, objectives, and structure of the deliverable, outlining the context of U2Demo and its role in establishing the foundations for interoperability, cybersecurity, and data privacy.
- **Section 2 – Questionnaire on Standards, Interoperability and Cybersecurity:**
Presents the results of a consortium-wide survey on current practices and requirements related to standards adoption, interoperability readiness, cybersecurity measures, and data privacy compliance.
- **Section 3 – Defining the Semantic Foundations for U2Demo Interoperability:**
Describes the methodology for developing a modular, FAIR-compliant ontology aligned with relevant standards (e.g., SAREF, SEAS, ENERSHARE) and illustrates its application to pilot use cases.
- **Section 4 – Interoperability Analysis:** Defines the interoperability interfaces for the U2Demo platform, including integration with Simpl Middleware and external data

exchange frameworks. It specifies API requirements and supported formats, illustrated with the EW Digital Spine Client as a reference implementation. Both RESTful and WebSocket APIs are outlined, along with supported JSON and file-based formats (CSV, TSV, XML), providing guidance for secure, standardised data exchange.

- **Section 5 – Cybersecurity and Data Privacy Considerations:** Outlines a tailored security framework addressing authentication, encryption, access control, and compliance with GDPR, NIS 2, and the forthcoming EU Network Code on Cybersecurity (NCCS).
- **Section 6 – Conclusions:** Summarizes the main findings, identifies implications for standardization and interoperability, and sets the next steps for implementation in pilot environments.

1.3 Relationship with other deliverables

This deliverable builds directly on the Business and System Use Cases defined in Task T1.4 [18] (described in earlier deliverables), which identify the actors, roles, and information flows across U2Demo pilots. The business objects and interaction models defined there serve as the foundation for the semantic modelling and interoperability requirements described here.

It also provides input for:

1. WP3 – The interoperability requirements, semantic models' foundations, and interface specifications defined in this deliverable will guide the development of the middleware components in T3.4 and further development of the data models. These components will act as the backbone of the U2Demo platform, enabling secure and standardised data exchange between the platform, active consumers, EC devices, external stakeholders, and data spaces (e.g., Simpl Middleware). The mappings, ontology alignments, and interoperability principles presented here will be directly applied in the design of device interfaces (smart meters, actuators, IoT devices), market and system operator APIs.
2. WP4 – The interoperability framework and ontology specified here will ensure that the P2P trading, energy sharing, and flexibility optimisation algorithms developed in WP4 can integrate seamlessly into the U2Demo platform. By providing a consistent representation of data across pilots and external systems, this deliverable facilitates the implementation of robust, reusable, and market-compliant algorithms that can interact with the future U2Demo platform.
3. WP5 – In WP5, the methodologies and tools developed in U2Demo will be tested and validated in four diverse pilot sites. The semantic interoperability foundations and integration requirements defined here will enable consistent deployment of the platform across different technical environments, governance models, and regulatory contexts. This deliverable supports WP5 by ensuring that pilot implementations can exchange data reliably, integrate with local assets, and demonstrate the effectiveness of the tools in promoting Distributed Energy Resource (DER) adoption and EC integration.
4. WP6 - The semantic model and interoperability specifications from this deliverable will inform WP6 activities on standardisation and harmonisation (T6.2 [19]). By documenting the U2Demo interoperability requirements and their alignment with existing standards (e.g., SAREF, SEAS, Common Information Model - CIM), this

deliverable provides a reference for engagement with standardisation bodies. WP6 will leverage these outputs to advocate for standards that enable interoperable and replicable P2P energy sharing systems.

2 Questionnaire on Standards, Interoperability and Cybersecurity

In this section, the results and context of the questionnaire on Standards, Interoperability, and Cybersecurity (check in APPENDIX A: Questionnaire on Standards, Interoperability, and Cybersecurity) are introduced as a key instrument deployed under Task T3.2 – “Standards, Interoperability, and Cybersecurity”. Since the task is focusing on ensuring that the U2Demo platform is built upon a solid foundation of open standards, secure interfaces, and interoperable architectures, the assessment of these characteristics is relevant not only for technical performance but also for maximizing replicability, scalability, and usability by a broad spectrum of stakeholders operating under diverse regulatory and infrastructural conditions.

The questionnaire was designed to support these objectives by gathering technical input from partners regarding existing practices and system capabilities. It addressed key topics such as standards adoption, data interoperability, cybersecurity, and integration readiness, forming the basis for the subsequent analyses.

The questionnaire was distributed to all consortium members; however, responses were received exclusively from partners directly involved in the U2Demo pilot implementations. This proved advantageous, as it ensured complete coverage of the four pilot sites (Portugal, Italy, the Netherlands, and Belgium) and guaranteed that the feedback was grounded in the operational realities of each context. In total, six consortium partners provided input: EDP R&D (PT), INESC-ID (PT), Watt-IS (PT), ENGREEN (IT), DHAAG (NL), and KLIMAAN (BE). Given their direct role in the design, deployment, and day-to-day operation of the pilots, these respondents represent the most relevant source of information, ensuring that the findings have strong traction in the field and directly reflect the needs and constraints of real-world implementation.

2.1 Objectives and Design of the Questionnaire

The principal motivation behind the questionnaire was to collect structured technical input from partners directly involved in the pilot deployments and platform development. It serves as a tool to identify the degree to which existing solutions are aligned with the principles and objectives of U2Demo in terms of data exchange capabilities, cybersecurity robustness, and semantic interoperability. Furthermore, the questionnaire acts as a preparatory step for subsequent mapping and integration activities, including the definition of interfaces between the U2Demo platform and relevant frameworks such as Simpl Middleware [8]. The results provide a clear snapshot of the pilots’ technological maturity and highlight specific requirements to be addressed in the U2Demo platform’s development, directly informing the work in T3.3 – Development of P2P Energy Sharing Platform Using Blockchain Technologies and T3.4 – Internal and External Interfaces and Middleware.

2.1.1 Strategic Objectives

More specifically, the questionnaire was designed to support the following key objectives:

- To characterize the current adoption of relevant standards (e.g., OPENADR [20], SAREF, Open Charge Point Interface (OCPI) [21], [22], CIM [23], Building Information Modelling (BIM) [24], Block Element Modifier (BEM), IEC-61850 [25]) across pilot

partners, with the goal of identifying gaps, redundancies, and opportunities for standard alignment or extension;

- To understand the extent of interoperability achieved or required within pilot partners systems, particularly in what concerns the interfaces, protocols, data models, and ontologies used for information exchange within U2Demo Platform and with external platforms;
- To identify and document cybersecurity and data privacy practices already implemented by partners, including mechanisms for encryption, secure communication, identity verification, access control, and regulatory compliance (notably with GDPR);
- To evaluate the technological readiness and alignment with emerging European initiatives, including the potential integration of Simpl Middleware as part of a secure and federated energy data infrastructure;
- To collect qualitative feedback and identify pilot-specific constraints, such as regulatory limitations, proprietary system dependencies, or technical bottlenecks that could impact platform interoperability or platform data integration.

These objectives directly derivates from the broader aims of Task 3.2, which include performing a systematic mapping of data exchange needs (as defined in Task 1.4 [18]) to the functions and needs considered in the existing standards, and determining whether extensions or adaptations are needed. In addition, cybersecurity requirements are to be outlined in light of the identified practices and perceived risks, and an initial evaluation of the feasibility of confidential computing technologies is also within the scope.

2.1.2 Structure and Design Methodology

The questionnaire was structured around three primary thematic pillars: **Standards and Interoperability**, **Pilot Data Exchange and Integration**, and **Cybersecurity and Data Privacy**. Each section included a mix of closed-ended and open-ended questions, allowing partners to provide both definitive answers and contextual information drawn from operational experience.

- The Standards and Interoperability section explored the current usage of technical standards and communication protocols across partner systems. It further inquired about limitations in existing standards, efforts to propose extensions, and previous experiences in integrating heterogeneous platforms. Questions were framed to elicit concrete references to both sector-wide and domain-specific standards.
- The Pilot Data Interoperability section targeted the technical aspects of existing pilots of data collection, exchange, and synchronization in each pilot. Pilot partners were asked to detail supported data formats, acquisition mechanisms (e.g., APIs, Secure File Transfer Protocol (sFTP), IoT devices), and the nature of data flows (e.g., unidirectional, bidirectional, or real-time). This was essential to assess compatibility with the U2Demo architecture and to anticipate integration needs/constraints.

- The Cybersecurity and Data Privacy section investigated the security degree of partner infrastructures. It covered encryption methods, authentication schemes, asset protection strategies, and practices for regulatory compliance. Attention was also given to identifying cyber threats faced in past projects and whether advanced technologies such as anomaly detection, secure enclaves, or blockchain have been considered.

The questionnaire concluded with a section for “additional observations”, giving respondents the opportunity to raise any technical concerns, regulatory insights, or integration suggestions that were not addressed in the main body of questions. This qualitative input is valuable for informing both the architectural evolution of the platform and the strategic direction of Work Packages and respective Tasks that follow.

The design of the questionnaire was deliberately collaborative and iterative, ensuring relevance across technical, regulatory, and operational perspectives. Drafts were reviewed internally by Task 3.2 participants before distribution, to ensure alignment with project goals and technical completeness. As a result, the responses collected through this instrument aim to play a relevant role in shaping the technical specifications and integration strategies of the U2Demo platform.

2.2 Summary of Questionnaire Findings

This chapter presents only the key insights from the questionnaire responses, aggregated across the main thematic areas. The full set of answers, together with the detailed question-by-question analysis for each partner, is provided in APPENDIX B: Questionnaire Answers and complete analysis, for readers requiring a deeper review.

The questionnaire responses offer a consolidated view of the technical landscape across the four U2Demo pilot sites, highlighting both commonalities and divergences in their current setups.

On standards adoption, partners reported a mix of open and proprietary solutions. Some pilots already integrate well-established standards such as SAREF, SEAS, CIM, OPENADR, and IEC 61850 into their platforms, while others rely heavily on proprietary data models or protocols tailored to local contexts. The use of Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP) [26], [27], [28] and OCPI was noted in pilots involving Electric Vehicle (EV) charging integration, and certain partners indicated plans to expand their standards adoption as part of U2Demo’s implementation phase.

Regarding interoperability, few pilots already have API-based communication mechanisms in place, though the underlying data formats vary from JSON and XML to CSV and custom schemas. Communication protocols such as Hypertext Transfer Protocol/ Representational State Transfer (HTTP/REST), Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT), and Modbus were frequently mentioned, alongside proprietary solutions. While some partners have partial semantic mapping capabilities, none reported full ontology-based interoperability at present, underscoring the need for a unified semantic layer within U2Demo.

In terms of cybersecurity, maturity levels differ significantly. Not many pilots currently employ TLS encryption, PKI-based authentication, and multi-factor authentication for sensitive operations, while others rely on more basic measures such as username/password credentials

and minimal encryption. Role-based access control is widely used, but attribute-based or policy-driven access control is less common. Few partners currently operate intrusion detection or anomaly detection systems, suggesting an opportunity for harmonisation and improvement across pilots.

For data privacy, all respondents acknowledged GDPR compliance as a requirement, but the degree of implementation varies. Some pilots already apply privacy-by-design principles, explicit consent management processes, and data minimisation strategies, whereas others have only partially implemented these measures. The treatment of personal data, particularly in areas like household energy consumption, also varied, with some partners anonymising all datasets while others retain identifiable information under strict access control.

Overall, the aggregated results reveal a heterogeneous starting point: certain pilots are technically advanced in specific domains, while others are still evolving toward full compliance with U2Demo's interoperability, security, and privacy ambitions. These differences reinforce the need for a common semantic model, harmonised cybersecurity baseline, and standardised privacy practices, all of which are addressed in the subsequent sections of this deliverable.

2.2.1 Key Findings and Requirements on Standards, Interoperability and Cybersecurity for U2Demo Platform

The U2Demo project unites a multidisciplinary consortium to design, implement, and validate peer-to-peer (P2P) energy sharing and flexibility markets through user-centric platforms and real-world pilots in Portugal, Italy, the Netherlands, and Belgium. The aggregated analysis identifies strategic requirements, technical challenges, and needs for the U2Demo platform.

1. Shared Vision: Towards Empowered and Engaged Energy Citizens

Across responses, a common thread was the importance of designing platforms that empower end-users (citizens, households, or building managers) to actively participate in energy sharing and flexibility mechanisms. Partners agreed that such platforms must go beyond technical excellence to offer clear value propositions for users, including:

- Visibility of energy flows, costs and benefits.
- Tools for informed decision-making.
- Real-time or near-real-time feedback on consumption and savings.
- Incentives for participation in energy communities.

While some pilots (e.g. Watt-Is in Portugal) already have tools under development or deployed, others are in the ideation phase. Despite different stages of implementation, all expressed a desire to co-design with users' solutions.

2. Platform Requirements: Modularity, Interoperability, and Usability

Most partners stressed the need for flexible, modular platforms that can adapt to varying pilot realities. These include different types of dwellings, user profiles, legacy infrastructures, and regional regulations.

Interoperability is a critical enabler. Solutions should:

- Compatibility with existing data acquisition systems and diverse energy assets (Photovoltaic (PV), storage, EV charging).

- Support for open communication standards.

Ease of use was also highlighted: platforms should cater to a wide range of digital skills and include accessible, intuitive interfaces. Support for multiple languages and customizable dashboards was also mentioned as desirable.

3. Backend Capabilities: Settlement, Forecasting, and Optimization

A key differentiator for the U2Demo platform is its ability to handle P2P energy transactions, energy sharing models and local flexibility exchange. Several partners pointed out that:

- Transparent settlement algorithms are needed to gain user trust.
- Billing must accurately reflect complex interactions and variable tariffs.
- Forecasting of consumption and generation is crucial for optimization.
- Simulation or sandbox environments for testing pricing schemes and market configurations.

Existing tools, such as Watt-IS's SOL13 - Settlement and Billing tool and SOL14 - User interface and data analytics, were noted as potential reusable components, offering support to the settlement of the P2P markets and to provide key information for the ECs members.

4. Key Barriers: Regulation, Data Privacy, and User Motivation

The implementation of P2P energy sharing includes challenges such as:

- Regulatory uncertainty was the most cited challenge. National frameworks vary greatly and may not always support dynamic pricing, energy communities, or third-party aggregators.
- Data privacy and ownership remain sensitive topics, especially when dealing with granular energy consumption/injection data.
- User engagement is not guaranteed. Several partners noted that behavioural aspects (trust, convenience, perceived benefit) must be considered alongside technology.

Suggested mitigation measures include regulatory mapping, GDPR-compliant consent and anonymisation processes, and active user co-creation.

5. Opportunities for Cross-Pilot Collaboration and Knowledge Exchange

Despite differences in geography, scope, and technical readiness, the analysis revealed substantial potential for collaboration:

- Many partners are facing similar questions around platform design, user interface, market mechanisms, and regulation.
- Pilots can benefit from shared lessons learned, reusable tools, and templates (e.g., User Experience (UX) designs, APIs, dashboards, tools, etc).
- Cross-pilot comparisons could strengthen the validation of results and support broader replication in other EU regions.

It was suggested that joint workshops or thematic working groups (e.g., on user engagement, regulatory mapping, or interoperability standards) be organized within the project to maximize learning.

6. Cybersecurity for U2Demo Platform: Key Findings

Cybersecurity maturity varies widely. Some partners (e.g., Watt-IS, DHAAG) implement TLS encryption, authentication layers, basic intrusion detection, and early-stage auditing; others lack even basic protections such as secure communication protocols or access control. Key observations include:

- Limited awareness or experience with advanced security measures such as confidential computing, though interest exists in secure-by-design, managed infrastructure solutions.
- Mixed GDPR compliance: a minority use robust consent and anonymisation processes; others rely on generic privacy statements without technical enforcement.
- Absence of advanced safeguards such as dispute resolution mechanisms, smart contract auditing, and defences against false or malicious data injection.

While current regulation may not yet demand these capabilities, their absence could become a bottleneck if peer-to-peer energy transactions become more common.

Not surprisingly, most partners seem open to strengthening their cybersecurity posture. There is interest in better protocols, improved access control models, and support for threat detection. This revealed the need to introduce a coherent framework that provides practical tools and a common baseline for platform integration (That may include technical templates for key procedures (incident response, data processing), shared policy recommendations, and introductory sessions to support capacity building).

The findings confirm the need for a unified, practical cybersecurity baseline for all pilots, covering authentication, encryption, access control, monitoring, and incident response, as well as privacy-by-design measures

The aggregated findings from the questionnaire provide a clear picture of the pilots' current technical landscape, revealing both common requirements and significant disparities in standards adoption, interoperability readiness, and cybersecurity maturity. These insights form a direct input to the design of the U2Demo semantic data model and interoperability framework, ensuring that the platform addresses real operational needs while harmonising practices across diverse contexts. Building on this foundation, the next chapter defines the U2Demo information exchange model and details the methodology applied to develop a modular, standards-aligned ontology capable of supporting secure, consistent, and scalable data exchange among all pilot sites.

3 Defining the Semantic Foundations for U2Demo Interoperability

The U2Demo project relies on a complex ecosystem of actors, devices, and services that interact continuously to support the energy sharing, flexibility, trading and billing functions of energy communities. To enable such coordination, a well-structured information exchange model is required, one that accommodates the heterogeneity of energy assets, user roles, legal frameworks, and optimization logics across different pilot sites. This section aims to map the critical information flows between the involved actors (e.g., EC members, EC managers, Distribution System Operators (DSOs), suppliers, and aggregators) and formalize the types, frequency, and granularity of the data exchanged, according to a common ontology.

This section also presents the initial core modules of the U2Demo ontology and aims to show how data is shared throughout the life cycle of energy community operations: from day-ahead scheduling and real-time operation to settlement and billing. To ground the proposed information exchange model, we focus on one representative scenario drawn from the U2Demo pilots. This scenario serves as a concrete example for applying the core modules and semantic structures defined in the initial draft of the U2Demo ontology. By aligning the information flows with ontology concepts, such as actors, assets, forecasts, market data, and control actions, we illustrate how semantic modelling supports traceability, interoperability, and data consistency across diverse community configurations. This approach ensures that the ontology is not developed in abstraction, but is directly validated against the operational realities of energy communities.

3.1 Methodology for the definition of a Semantic Data Model and Ontology

To design the semantic data model for the U2Demo project we leverage on the approach of AIME, an agile ontology development methodology tailored for European data spaces (EDS) with a focus on FAIR data principles [6]. Developed within the OMEGA-X energy data space project [29], AIME fosters the reuse of standards and ontologies through interaction models that capture data exchanges. It promotes agile practices to facilitate stakeholder collaboration, enabling modular, FAIR-compliant ontologies for complex, multi-actor data environments. Although U2Demo is not a Data Space project this methodology seems to be an adequate fit for the project and for the alignment with the European Commission objectives.

The suggested methodology is based on 7 principles, which are as follows:

1. **Target modularity.** A modular approach allows independent development and maintenance of ontology segments tailored to different domains or use cases, while still ensuring overall cohesion. The European energy sector, for instance, includes stakeholders ranging from grid operators and regulators to energy communities and consumers, all of whom may use distinct data formats and standards. As data flows grow in volume and complexity, especially with the rise of distributed energy resources, EV integration, and real-time demand response, ensuring semantic clarity becomes critical. To support this, the ontology development methodology must accommodate heterogeneous data with differing levels of structure and semantic richness and foster alignment between existing reference ontologies and domain-specific vocabularies.
2. **Ensure FAIR compliance.** Design the ontology for human and machine readability, supporting findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability to enable scalable integration.

3. **Use case–driven.** Base ontology development on real use cases, modelling agent-based data interactions. Leverage insights from European projects (e.g., INTERCONNECT [30], PLATOON [31], ENERSHARE [32], OMEGA-X [29], [33]) that applied ontologies like SEAS, SAREF, CIM to similar contexts.
4. **Be agile.** Apply iterative, collaborative development with incremental refinement and stakeholder involvement throughout the ontology lifecycle.
5. **Align with existing standards.** The methodology must ensure alignment to reference standards and data models. Without such alignment, ontologies risk becoming siloed and incompatible with legacy systems or emerging technologies.
6. **Reuse existing ontologies.** Incorporate established ontologies (SEAS [3], SAREF [1], [2], CIM [23], Smart Data Models [34]) where possible, extending only when necessary
7. **Support the full ontology lifecycle.** Cover requirements specification, implementation, publication, and maintenance, using collaborative tools (e.g., GitLab) and continuous integration to ensure sustainability, traceability, and robustness.

The suggested methodology to create and maintain the semantic data model for the U2Demo project is presented in the Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1 – Steps of the methodology to create the U2Demo ontology

The application of Step 1 takes place prior to initiating the ontology engineering process and is essential for conducting a comprehensive analysis of the requirements and specifications expected from the ontology or semantic data model. This preparatory phase begins with a detailed examination of the U2Demo use cases (UCs), which define the core application scenarios, the ontology is intended to support. In the context of the U2Demo project, each use case was documented following the IEC 62559 template, which ensures a standardized and comprehensive description of pilot-specific operational and informational requirements [35], [36], [37]. Particular attention is given to the Business Objects (BOs) defined within each UC entry in the repository, as these serve as key elements for analysing the interactions between actors and systems. A critical aspect of this step involves the extraction of relevant domain-specific concepts, relationships, and entities, such as sensors, buildings, and energy consumption, along with their corresponding attributes (e.g., sensor type, location). These extracted elements form the foundational building blocks for the subsequent semantic modelling process. The output of this step are these backlogs of UCs and concepts/BOs that are the input for the next step of the methodology.

The second step of the methodology, once the requirements have been formalized through the use case analysis, the next step involves examining existing ontologies to identify reusable semantic components. This begins with a specification of the ontology requirements based on the BOs and concepts identified in Step 1. These requirements guide the search and evaluation of ontologies that may already capture parts of the desired knowledge domain. The process involves scanning an inventory of existing ontologies, potentially including domain-specific, cross-domain, and upper-level ontologies to assess their relevance, granularity, and compatibility. The analysis phase evaluates whether these ontologies align structurally and semantically with the project's needs, taking into account aspects such as class hierarchies, property definitions, and logical consistency. Selected ontologies are then shortlisted for reuse, extension, or integration in subsequent steps.

With both the requirements and the candidate ontologies defined, the process proceeds to a mapping and gap analysis phase (Step 3). For each concept or BO in the backlog, a semantic comparison is conducted to determine whether an equivalent or sufficiently similar concept exists in the selected ontologies. If a match is found, the concept is flagged for reuse, ensuring alignment with existing standards and promoting interoperability. In cases where no suitable representation exists/was found, a gap is identified, and a new concept is created and defined accordingly. This iterative process continues until all backlog elements have been evaluated. This step is essential for minimizing redundancy, promoting semantic consistency, and managing the ontology's modular growth over time.

After completing the mapping and gap analysis, the next phase involves the formal construction of ontology modules. Each module corresponds to a coherent subset of the domain and encapsulates a group of related concepts and relationships. The modular approach ensures scalability, reusability, and easier maintenance.

The development of these modules follows established ontology modelling practices (e.g., using Web Ontology Language - OWL, Resource Description Framework Schema - RDF/S, Shapes Constraint Language - SHACL), and is typically carried out in close collaboration with domain experts and stakeholders (in this case the project pilot partners). Their feedback is instrumental in validating the conceptual accuracy of classes, properties, axioms, and constraints. The outcome of this step is a collection of well-defined, interoperable semantic modules representing the domain knowledge.

Once the individual ontology modules are formalized, they are integrated into a harmonized ontology. This step addresses semantic alignment across modules and with any reused external ontologies. It involves resolving naming conflicts, aligning class hierarchies, standardizing property usage, and ensuring logical consistency.

The harmonization phase may also involve semantic enrichment, where additional axioms or metadata are introduced to improve inferencing capabilities and semantic precision. The resulting ontology must undergo validation from both a technical and stakeholder perspective. This includes evaluating whether the ontology accurately reflects the domain requirements.

The final step in the methodology addresses the deployment and sustainability of the ontology. After harmonization, the ontology is officially released, published in a shared repository (e.g., GitHub), and documented with versioning and metadata.

Ongoing maintenance is a critical aspect of this step. It includes updating the ontology to reflect evolving domain knowledge, integrating new feedback and updates from stakeholders, and supporting the onboarding of additional use cases. A control mechanism is embedded into the workflow: when a new use case is introduced, the process loops back to Step 1, ensuring that the ontology evolves incrementally and remains aligned with project objectives and emerging requirements.

Building on the identification of the information exchange needs, the next step is to define how these requirements translate into a structured semantic framework. Section 3.2 presents the methodology adopted for developing the U2Demo ontology, ensuring that it captures the necessary concepts, relationships, and constraints to support interoperability across all pilot contexts.

3.2 Methodology application for U2Demo

The aim of this section is to illustrate how the proposed methodology is applied to the use cases from the U2Demo pilot sites, based on the current state of definition at the time of writing this deliverable. The ontology development methodology applied in U2Demo builds on proven practices from European interoperability initiatives [1], [2], [3], [7], [38], [39], adapting them to the project's specific technical, operational, and regulatory context. It is structured to ensure semantic precision, compatibility with established standards, and practical applicability across diverse pilot environments.

3.2.1 Identified data, entities and communication flows in U2Demo Use Cases

For the U2Demo project, ten Business Use Cases (BUCs) were identified in the Task 1.4 – *Definition of Business and System Use Cases for U2Demo Pilots* [18]. The models of these BUCs show the objectives of the BUCs, the participating roles and the information flows between the roles. The repository includes BUCs covering the current operation, as well as operations of the ECs in the future, with additional flexible assets and flexibility markets and new market structures for energy sharing, including P2P markets. To define the BUCs, the IEC 62559-2:2015 standard was used, providing the basis for a common use case management repository, facilitating their harmonization to establish broadly accepted generic use cases as a foundation for further standardization efforts [36]. This standard defines a structured template for use cases, including actor lists, requirements list, information exchange list, etc.

The BUCs were identified through meetings with the pilot leaders in which the priorities and the needs of the pilots were summarized. As a result, the following categories of the BUCs emerged:

- Current operation of the EC
- Operation of the EC with energy sharing and P2P models
- Operation of the EC with flexibility/ancillary services

All BUCs consist of multiple scenarios, e.g. scheduling, operation and billing (more details on the BUCs modelled in Task 1.4). Since the pilot sites of the U2Demo project have significant differences in the governance and the energy sharing models, the BUCs are pilot-site specific. However, they can be easily applied to ECs with similar layouts.

The information exchanged between the participating roles is referred to as BOs. These BOs are of particular relevance for the assessment of the standards to follow when developing the U2Demo ontology and platform. The complete list of BOs modelled in Task 1.4. is presented in APPENDIX C: BOs list, and will be used for thorough assessment of the possible standards to be used in the platform in Section 3.2 .

To illustrate the data flows established in one of the pilots, the scenario “Day-ahead scheduling” of the demo site in the Netherlands was chosen. In this scenario, two roles are involved: the Grid Energy Management System (GEMS) and the Home Energy Management System (HEMS). This scenario occurs each day and models the scheduling phase for the operation of the EC the next day. In the following, the activities in this scenario are presented, with their description and the BOs exchanged. The description of the BOs for this scenario is given in Table 3-1. The activities in this scenario include:

1. *Request numerical weather prediction data*: The GEMS requests numerical weather prediction data through an API.
2. *PV prediction and consumption forecast*: The GEMS computes a forecast for the PV production and the consumption of each EC member. This forecast is based on the numerical weather prediction data, on historical consumption and production data of the EC members and possible a-priori knowledge such as know car schedules, festival agenda, etc.
 - BO sent: Forecast information for one HEMS
3. *Request energy prices*: The GEMS requests the energy prices in the day-ahead (DA) energy market.
4. *Define EC internal price*: With knowledge on the PV production and energy consumption forecasts, and the current prices for energy, the GEMS defines an EC internal energy price.
 - BO sent: EC energy prices
5. *Individual look-ahead energy resources scheduling*: The HEMS of each household optimizes its own flexible assets. In this step, different objective functions may be considered, such as: minimization of monetary cost, maximization of self-consumption, maximization of the opportunity cost. In this pilot site, the flexible assets are mainly battery energy storage systems, heat pumps, PV and electric vehicles.
 - BO received: Forecast information for one HEMS (from activity 2), EC energy prices (from activity 4, later from activity 7)
 - BO sent: Scheduling information of a HEMS
6. *EC look ahead energy resources scheduling*: With the information of the schedule of each HEMS, the GEMS optimizes the community resources and sets new setpoints for import and export of each HEMS.
 - BO received: Scheduling information of a HEMS (from activity 5)
7. *Update EC internal energy price*: If the convergence criterion is not fulfilled, the EC internal energy prices are updated.
 - BO sent: EC energy prices
8. *Organize information about possible flexibility and the schedule*: In this step, the solution of the optimization problem is stored. The schedules for import and export of each HEMS are stored in order to be sent to the HEMS of the EC members. The consumption and injection forecasts of the whole EC are stored, to be sent to the DSO.
 - BO sent: EC member imp/exp scheduling

9. *Acknowledge the schedule*: Each HEMS acknowledges the schedule for its import and export values.
 - ➔ BO received: EC member imp/exp scheduling (from activity 8)

Figure 3-2 – Day-ahead scheduling of the pilot site in the Netherlands

Table 3-1: Overview of the content of the BOs of the day-ahead scheduling of the pilot site in the Netherlands

Name of the BO	Content of the BO
Forecast information for one HEMS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ID of the HEMS • Time stamp • Time series for the day in 15 min intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ PV production forecast ○ Consumption forecast
EC energy prices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time stamp • Time series for the day in 15 min intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Grid buy price (including transmission fees and taxes) ○ Grid sell price (including transmission fees and taxes) ○ Internal price of the energy community
Scheduling information of a HEMS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ID of the HEMS • Time stamp • Time series for the day in 15 min intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Power imported by this EC member ○ Power exported by this EC member
EC member Imp/Exp scheduling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ID of the HEMS • Time stamp • Time series for the day in 15 min intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Power imported to this EC member ○ Power exported from this EC member

3.2.2 Ontology analysis

The objective of Step 3 (see Figure 3-1) is to lay the semantic foundation for the U2Demo ontology by aligning the extracted concepts with well-established ontologies and, where necessary, designing new ontological modules following best practices in ontology engineering. This step is grounded in the principle of ontology reuse, which promotes leveraging existing, validated semantic models before creating new conceptual structures. By adhering to ontology design patterns, this phase ensures modularity, interoperability, and semantic consistency across the U2Demo ontology.

To operationalize this step, a set of key tasks is defined:

a) Concept and Relationship Identification

The first task involves mapping the list of extracted terms from Step 1 to formal semantic constructs. Each term or key notion is associated with a candidate concept or relationship to be used in the ontology. For example, the term "*pump*" might be mapped to the class *Pump*, while a more specific term like "*heat pump*" may be mapped to a subclass such as *HeatPump*. This semantic alignment ensures that the terminology used in the pilot use cases is explicitly captured in the ontology with well-defined semantics.

b) Reuse of Existing Ontologies

The second task focuses on identifying equivalent or closely related concepts in existing ontologies, such as SAREF, SEAS, ENERSHARE, PLATOON, or CIM. For each candidate concept, existing ontologies are scanned to determine whether a suitable definition already exists. If the same concept appears in multiple ontologies, mappings or alignments are proposed to ensure cross-domain interoperability. Particular attention is paid to the correct classification of relationships, distinguishing between hierarchical and structural relations, to preserve ontological clarity and prevent semantic ambiguity.

c) Design New Ontological Modules

In cases where relevant concepts are not found in existing ontologies, or when domain-specific extensions are required to cover U2Demo use cases, new ontological modules are designed. These modules are developed to integrate seamlessly with reused ontologies, ensuring that extensions remain modular and interoperable. It is common that a single use case may require the introduction of several interrelated new concepts, which are grouped and encapsulated within a coherent ontological module tailored to the needs of the domain.

By structuring Step 3 around reusing first principles and modular design, the U2Demo ontology is both grounded in semantic web standards and adaptable to the specificities of energy communities, facilitating a robust and scalable semantic data model.

For that in the Step 2, a comprehensive review of existing ontologies was conducted to identify reusable semantic components relevant to the U2Demo context. The following ontologies and their domain-specific extensions were analysed:

- **SAREF**² (Smart Applications REFerence ontology) and its domain extensions:
 - SAREF4ENER - extension for the Energy Flexibility domain, enabling semantic representation of energy-related devices and services.
 - SAREF4BLDG - extension for the Building domain, covering concepts such as building zones, systems, and environmental conditions.
 - SAREF4GRID - focuses on extending SAREF in order to create a common core of general concepts for smart grid data oriented to the IoT field. The main idea is to identify the core components, as mentioned, that could be extended for particular smart grid subdomains
- **SEAS**³ (Smart Energy Aware Systems) – an ontology framework emphasizing context-aware energy data modeling, time series, and flexibility.
- **ENERSHARE**⁴ ontology developed to support data exchange and interoperability in energy sharing scenarios, particularly within energy communities in some of the project pilots
- **CIM**⁵ (Common Information Model) – a well-established standard from the IEC for representing electrical networks and system components.

² <https://saref.etsi.org/>

³ <https://ci.mines-stetienne.fr/seas/index.html>

⁴ <https://github.com/EnershareProject/EnershareOntologies>

⁵ https://ontology.tno.nl/IEC_CIM/

- **PLATOON⁶** ontology – developed in the context of the PLATOON project to support industrial data interoperability and energy use case modeling.
- **INTERCONNECT⁷** ontology – aimed at enabling semantic interoperability across heterogeneous smart home and energy devices and services.

A special highlight is given to the SAREF4ENER extension due to its close correlation with the purpose of the U2Demo project, particularly in enabling semantic interoperability for smart energy management at the building and community level. SAREF4ENER is an OWL-DL ontology developed as an extension of the SAREF core ontology for the energy domain, formalized in ETSI TS 103 410-1 [38]. It supports semantic interoperability among smart appliances, energy management systems (EMS), and resource managers (RM) within smart homes and buildings. The ontology is based on the CENELEC EN 50631 ("Household appliances network and grid connectivity" series) and EN 50491-12-2 ("General requirements for Home and Building Electronic Systems (HBES) and Building Automation and Control Systems (BACS)") standards [40], [41], and integrates key elements from SPINE and S2 protocols to enable harmonized data exchange for energy flexibility and optimization.

SAREF4ENER facilitates demand response scenarios by modelling device behaviour, energy consumption/production profiles, power limits, flexibility capabilities, and user preferences. It enables interoperable data exchange between energy smart devices and stakeholders such as DSOs, aggregators, and service providers. The ontology has been adopted as a reference semantic model in the European Commission's Code of Conduct for Energy Smart Appliances to promote device interoperability across the EU market which further reinforces its relevance as a semantic foundation for the U2Demo ontology.

3.2.3 Mapping between the UCs and existing ontologies

To support clarity, reusability, and scalability, the U2Demo ontology adopts a modular design approach, a widely used technique in ontology engineering for managing complexity. Modularization enables the ontology to be structured around distinct yet interrelated semantic domains, allowing each module to be developed, maintained, and reused independently or in combination with others.

From all the U2Demo pilots were identified 10 core domains that structure the initial version of the U2Demo ontology. The core modules are:

1. **System:** defines the taxonomy of systems or assets;
2. **Player:** defines the taxonomy of actors, stakeholders and roles;
3. **Market:** focus on the taxonomy of the different markets addressed in U2Demo pilots;
4. **Forecast:** semantic structures to represent property forecasts;
5. **TimeSeries:** modeling of profiles such as consumption, generation, flexibility, and price, etc.;
6. **Schedule:** represents the taxonomy and relations related with the act of scheduling events,
7. **Device:** characterizes devices used across the U2Demo pilots;
8. **Event:** defines the taxonomy for the notion of event according to the U2Demo pilots;
9. **Price:** semantic relations related to energy pricing structures;
10. **Properties:** representation of properties and their evaluations across all domains.

⁶ <https://github.com/PLATOONProject/SEDMOON>

⁷ <https://gitlab.inesctec.pt/interconnect-public/ontology>

The following diagrams (from Figure 3-3 to Figure 3-12) present the initial structure of the 10 ontological modules identified for U2Demo. These modules are designed to be interoperable and can be extended or aligned with external ontologies as needed. The diagrams below provide a high-level overview of the internal structure of each core module, highlighting only the concepts newly introduced within the U2Demo scope (in orange boxes) to address gaps in existing ontologies, and illustrating how these concepts relate to reused semantic elements (in grey boxes). They do not depict all ontological concepts from the existing models that will be used in U2Demo; rather, they focus on the required extensions and their integration with, and relation to, the established semantic components.

In the diagrams, classes are represented as rectangles. Relationships (object properties) between entities are represented as arrows. Arrows are additionally used to represent some RDF, RDF-S and OWL constructs, more precisely: plain arrows with white triangles represent the *rdfs:subClassOf* relation between two classes. The origin of the arrow shall be considered as the subclass of the entity at the destination of the arrow. Dashed arrows accompanied by the expression *rdf:type* are used to indicate that the individual at the origin of the arrow is an instance of the class placed at the end of the arrow. Dashed arrows between two classes indicate a local restriction in the origin class, i.e. that the object property can be instantiated between the classes in the origin and the destination of the arrow. The identifier of the object property is indicated within the arrow. Datatype properties and class restrictions are presented as plain text.

3.2.3.1 System module

The System module uses mostly existing definitions from SEAS, Platoon and SAREF, namely S4ENER. From the U2Demo pilots there was only identified the need to create the definition of flexibility asset (*u2d-dvc:FlexibilityAsset*). Although this is part of the device module in the Figure 3-3 is shown how this concept is included in the system module for enhanced interoperability and information enrichment. In the context of U2Demo, *u2d-dvc:FlexibilityAsset* is one of the following subclasses: Heat Pumps (*seas:HeatPump*), PV (*seas:SolarPanel*), EV (*seas:ElectricVehicle*) and Storage (*s4ener:Storage*).

To address gaps identified in the reviewed ontologies, U2Demo introduces the *u2d-dvc:FlexibilityAsset* concept. This class allows any system or device capable of providing flexibility services, including demand shifting, generation adjustment, or storage management, to be explicitly identified and linked to scheduling, forecasting, and market interactions.

Figure 3-3 – U2Demo System Ontological Module

3.2.3.2 Player module

This module focuses on the taxonomy of players. In U2Demo project all pilots use the notion of player and several of them were reused from SEAS Player ontology (*seas:*) and ENERSHARE player ontology (*ener-play:*). The diagram (Figure 3-4) illustrates the set of players required across the pilots, showing that several of them are not currently represented in the existing ontologies reviewed and were included in the U2Demo player ontological module (*u2d-play:*). Notably, concepts such as HEMS, GEMS, Energy Community Member, and Energy Community Manager were absent from the ontologies analysed. These concepts have therefore been introduced into the U2Demo ontology as extensions of SEAS and ENERSHARE, ensuring that the player taxonomy fully supports the roles and interactions observed in the U2Demo pilots.

Key U2Demo extensions include:

- Energy Management Roles
 - *u2d-play:HouseEnergyManagementSystem* – representing household-level energy management systems with operational control over local devices.
 - *u2d-play:GridEnergyManagementSystem* – representing grid or community-level energy management systems coordinating multiple assets and actors.
- Market and Platform Roles
 - *u2d-play:MarketActor* – a generalised role for participants in market operations, extended with *u2d-play:BalanceResponsibleParty* for those accountable for balancing obligations.
 - *u2d-play:Platform* – representing generic platforms, extended with *u2d-play:FlexibilityMarketPlatform* for entities operating or facilitating flexibility trading.
 - *u2d-play:Supplier* – representing suppliers in the community or market context.
- Community-Specific Roles
 - *u2d-play:EnergyCommunityMember* – generic member of an energy community, specialised into:
 - *u2d-play:ActiveEnergyCommunityMember* – members actively participating in energy trading or flexibility provision.
 - *u2d-play:PassiveEnergyCommunityMember* – members primarily consuming energy without active participation.
 - *u2d-play:EnergyCommunityMemberWithPV* – members contributing local PV generation.
 - *u2d-play:EnergyCommunityMemberWithoutPV* – members without local PV generation assets.
 - *u2d-play:EnergyCommunityManager* – the coordinating role responsible for managing operations and interactions within the energy community.
- Specialised Providers
 - *u2d-play:IncentiveSettlementProvider* – entities responsible for calculating and settling incentives for flexibility or participation.
 - *u2d-play:EnergySharingBillingProvider* – entities managing billing processes for shared energy and community transactions.
- Ownership Roles
 - *u2d-play:HouseOwner* – owners of residential properties within the community.

- *u2d-play:EnergyAssetOwner* – owners of generation, storage, or flexibility assets.
- *u2d-play:SocialHouseCompany* – organisations managing social housing stock within the community.

Figure 3-4 – U2Demo Player Ontological Module

3.2.3.3 Market module

This module defines the taxonomy for market types and interactions addressed in U2Demo pilots, such as Electricity Market, Flexibility Market, and Ancillary Services Market. U2Demo introduces these to enable semantic modeling of local energy transactions and flexibility exchange within and across communities. These include *u2d-mrkt:AncillaryServicesMarket* for services that support grid stability, and *u2d-mrkt:FlexibilityMarket* as an overarching category

ahead scheduling, flexibility planning, and market participation within the U2Demo pilots and that allow differentiation between forecasts at household, building, and community aggregation levels.

3.2.3.5 TimeSeries module

The time series module defines the structure for profiles such as consumption, generation, flexibility, and price. SEAS, ENERSHARE and INTERCONNECT provide the base representation of time series data, which U2Demo extends with profile-specific semantics, including *u2d-ts:ECPVprofile*, *u2d-ts:ECMemberPVProfile*, *u2d-ts:MarketPriceProfile*, *u2d-ts:CreditPointsProfile*, *u2d-ts:HeatPumpProfile*, among others as can be seen in Figure 3-7 .

U2Demo extends this foundation with new domain specific profiles, including:

- *u2d-ts:ECPVProfile* and *u2d-ts:ECMemberPVProfile* – photovoltaic production profiles for the whole EC and for specified EC member;
- *u2d-ts:MarketPriceProfile* – temporal variation of market prices;
- *u2d-ts:GenerationProfile* – aggregated or asset-specific generation data;
- *u2d-ts:BatteryEnergyStorageSystemProfile* – charge/discharge patterns for storage;
- *u2d-ts:HeatPumpProfile* – heat pump operational profiles;
- *u2d-ts:EnergyCommunityInternalPriceProfile* – internal community pricing evolution;
- *u2d-ts:CreditPointsProfile* – points or credit-based incentive tracking over time.

These enhancements ensure compatibility with data semantic required to be exchanged in the pilots.

Figure 3-7 – U2Demo TimeSeries Ontological Module

3.2.3.6 Schedule module

This module describes the taxonomy and relations for scheduling events. While SEAS offer generic scheduling capabilities, U2Demo extends them with domain-specific concepts such as *u2d-scd:FlexibilitySchedule*. This is critical for representing operational plans generated within

the pilots' optimization and flexibility management processes. At its foundation, the module reuses the generic *sch:Schedule* and *ener-scd:ChargingSchedule* concepts to represent planned activities, such as electric vehicle charging (*seas:ElectricVehicleChargingStation*).

U2Demo introduces the broader *u2d-scd:FlexibilitySchedule* to explicitly model the scheduling of flexibility resources, as well as *u2d-dvc:FlexibilityAsset* to identify the resources associated with these schedules.

These extensions, particularly the explicit modeling of Flexibility Schedules and their forecast dependencies were not found in the existing ontologies analysed and were therefore added to the U2Demo ontology to support advanced scheduling and in the pilots.

Figure 3-8 – U2Demo Schedule Ontological Module

3.2.3.7 Device module

The device module defines the concept of devices used in U2Demo pilots. Many devices are reused from SAREF4ENER and SEAS, including Smart Meter, Storage, and Sensor. U2Demo adds only the concept of *u2d-dvc:FlexibilityAsset* relevant to energy community operation, which do not appear in the ontologies reviewed.

Figure 3-9 – U2Demo Device Ontological Module

3.2.3.8 Event module

The Event module in the U2Demo ontology formalizes the representation of operational and scheduling events relevant to energy community management. It builds on existing event

concepts from ENERSHARE (*ener-evnt:*) and PLATOON (*plt:*), while extending them with new U2Demo specific event types (*u2d-evnt:*) required by the pilots.

At its core, the module inherits from the generic *plt:Event* and *plt:ScheduledEvent* classes, enabling the representation of both instantaneous occurrences (e.g., alerts) and planned activities (e.g., scheduled charging sessions). From these base concepts, U2Demo defines additional event categories such as:

- Scheduling Events – Including *u2d-evnt:IndividualLookAheadEnergyScheduling*, *u2d-evnt:ECLookAheadEnergyScheduling*, and *u2d-evnt:HEMSScheduling*, which cover forward-looking operational planning for individual assets, households, and energy communities.
- Optimization Events – Extending *ener-evnt:OptimizationEvent* to include U2Demo-specific objectives, such as *u2d-evnt:MinimizationOfMonetaryCostOptimization*, *u2d-evnt:MaximizationOfOpportunityCostOptimization*, and *u2d-evnt:MaximizationOfCollectiveSelfConsumptionOptimization*.
- Activation Events – Represented by *u2d-evnt:ActivationEvent*, used when operational plans are triggered.
- Evaluation Events – Such as *u2d-evnt:PerformanceEvaluation* to assess the results of executed schedules or optimizations.

Several of these concepts have no direct equivalents in the ontologies analysed and were therefore introduced as U2Demo specific extensions. These extensions allow the ontology to explicitly model event-driven processes such as day-ahead scheduling, flexibility activation, congestion management, and cost or self-consumption optimization in energy communities.

This event structure ensures that U2Demo can capture the full lifecycle of operational actions, from planning and optimization to activation and post-event evaluation, while maintaining alignment with established ontological patterns from SEAS, ENERSHARE, and PLATOON.

Figure 3-10 – U2Demo Event Ontological Module

3.2.3.9 Price module

The Price module in the U2Demo ontology models the various types of prices and tariffs relevant to the pilots, ensuring that both market-based and community-specific pricing schemes can be represented. It builds upon existing concepts from SEAS (*seas:*) and ENERSHARE (*ener-price:*), while introducing a set of U2Demo-specific extensions (*u2d-price:*) to cover gaps identified in the analysis of existing ontologies.

At its foundation, the module reuses the generic *seas:Price* concept and its specialisation *seas:marketPrice*, providing a common structure for associating a price with a feature of interest, its value, unit of measurement, and applicable time period. From this base, U2Demo introduces the broader *u2d-price:EnergyPrice* class, which is then specialized into several domain-relevant subtypes:

- Market-related prices – including *u2d-price:MarketPriceForecast*, *u2d-price:RealTimeMarketPrice*, and *u2d-price:BidPrice* to represent price values at different stages of market operation.
- Community-related prices – such as *u2d-price:InternalCommunityPrice* for peer-to-peer or intra-community transactions.
- Flexibility-related prices – *u2d-price:FlexibilityPrice* to value the provision or activation of flexibility services.
- Retail and billing prices – *u2d-price:RetailerPrice* and *u2d-price:BillingPrice* for contractual or invoicing purposes.

The module retains interoperability with ENERSHARE’s price categorization by maintaining links to its *ener-price:hasInternalPrice*, *ener-price:hasTransactionPrice*, and *ener-price:hasRetailingPrice* properties. It also aligns with SEAS price property types, including *seas:BuyingPriceProperty*, *seas:SellingPriceProperty*, *seas:MarketPriceProperty*, and *seas:CostPriceProperty*.

Several of these price types, particularly Internal Community Price and Flexibility Price, were not present in any of the ontologies reviewed and have been introduced specifically to support U2Demo use cases. By combining reused and extended concepts, this module enables the ontology to represent pricing in a wide variety of operational contexts, from wholesale market participation to internal community trading and flexibility remuneration.

Figure 3-11 – U2Demo Price Ontological Module

3.2.3.10 Properties module

The Properties module is the most comprehensive and cross-cutting components of the U2Demo ontology. Unlike other modules that focus on a specific thematic domain, this module defines the semantic representation of properties across all domains in the ontology, providing a unified and consistent way to describe measurable or observable characteristics of systems, devices, markets, events, forecasts, etc..

Built upon foundational concepts from SEAS (*seas:Property*, *seas:FeatureOfInterest*, *seas:evaluation*) and enriched with property types from SAREF and ENERSHARE, this module ensures that the relevant aspects of the U2Demo pilots, from technical measurements to economic indicators, can be expressed in a machine-interpretable and interoperable form.

Properties may represent physical quantities (e.g., voltage, temperature, state of charge), performance indicators (e.g., efficiency, reliability), economic values (e.g., prices, tariffs, incentives), or flexibility-related attributes (e.g., available upward capacity, activation delay).

The cross-domain design means that these properties are not tied to a single context but are reused and specialised across modules. For example, a *PriceProperty* might be applied in the Market module, a *ConsumptionProperty* in the Time Series and Forecast modules, and a *FlexibilityProperty* in the System and Schedule modules. The module also supports property evaluations, linking a property to its current or forecasted value, unit of measurement, temporal scope, and source enabling the ontology to capture not only what is being measured but also how and when.

In the Figure 3-12 is presented as example the properties related with Electrical Power Properties from the Flexible Assets measurements.

Figure 3-12 – U2Demo Properties Ontological Module (example)

By providing this shared semantic backbone, the Properties module ensures semantic consistency, reusability, and interoperability across all other ontology modules. It is essential for aligning heterogeneous datasets in the U2Demo pilots, supporting both operational decision-making (e.g., scheduling, optimisation) and higher-level functions such as performance monitoring, reporting, and market settlement.

This ontology mapping exercise thus ensures semantic interoperability while preserving domain specific expressiveness and alignment with ongoing European standardization efforts. This high-level comparison provides a foundation for selecting and reusing relevant semantic resources in the U2Demo context, as shown. To build on this, the following sub-section presents a more detailed mapping between the concepts and BOs identified just in the example scenario of the Dutch pilot and the existing ontologies, focusing on the specific interactions and relationships involved and their mapping to the U2Demo suggested ontology.

3.2.3.11 Application to the Dutch pilot scenario

Based on this, and following again as example, the day-ahead scheduling scenario from the Dutch pilot site, the following main terms and concepts were identified as essential for semantic modelling in this U2Demo Dutch pilot scenario. These concepts were then assessed against the coverage offered by three reference ontologies (SAREF, SEAS, and ENERSHARE) to evaluate their suitability for reuse (Table 3-2).

Table 3-2: Mapping of some key concepts from Dutch pilot Scenario 1 to existing ontologies

Concept/Terms	SAREF	SEAS	ENERSHARE
Forecast	✓	✓	✓
- Production	✓	✓	☒
- Consumption	✓	✓	☒
- Weather	✓	✓	☒
Player	✓	✓	✓
- EC Manager	✗	✗	✗
- EC Member	✗	✗	✗
- Energy Community	✗	✗	✓
- HEMS	✗	✗	✗
- GEMS	✗	✗	✗
System	✓	✓	✓
- PV	✓	✓	☒
- Heat Pump	✗	✓	✗
- EV	✗	✓	☒
- Storage	✓	✓	☒
Price	✓	✓	✓
- Market price	✗	✓	☒
- Grid buy price	✗	✓	✗
- Grid sell price	✗	✓	✗
- Internal price	✗	✗	✗

✓ - Covered in
 ✗ - Not covered in
 ☒ - Reuses other existing ontologies

The analysis reveals that SEAS provides the most comprehensive support for contextual modelling (systems and players) and also energy prices. Its semantic structures are particularly suited for modelling Forecast and Price concepts, making it a strong candidate for representing temporal and contextual aspects of the data model. SAREF, especially through its extensions such as SAREF4ENER and SAREF4GRID, excels in modelling devices, time-series, schedules and forecasts, but lacks native support for actors, price models, and market structures. Developed under a European Data Space project, the ENERSHARE ontology reuses existing models, notably SAREF and SEAS, to ensure interoperability, as visible in the analysis, and provided several relevant extensions that are useful in the U2Demo context.

A key takeaway from this pilot related analysis confirms that none of the evaluated ontologies fully meets the U2Demo semantic requirements on its own. Each covers different but complementary aspects of the domain. As a result, the recommended strategy is a hybrid, modular approach, as already mentioned before: reuse mainly SAREF, SEAS and ENERSHARE for modelling each of the concepts and interactions. Where needed, new

U2Demo specific ontological modules were developed to bridge identified gaps, such as EC Manager, GEMS, internal pricing, and some forecast and events structures.

This ontology mapping exercise thus ensures semantic interoperability while preserving domain specific expressiveness and alignment with ongoing European standardization efforts. This high-level comparison provides a foundation for selecting and reusing relevant semantic resources in the U2Demo context.

Following with the U2Demo ontology fully structured into its core modules (Section 3.2.3.1 to Section 3.2.3.10), the next step is to demonstrate its practical applicability into the Scenario 1 from the Dutch pilot, which focuses on day-ahead scheduling within an energy community. This scenario provides a concrete setting in which to map the identified concepts, relationships, and data flows to actual pilot activities, showing how the ontology supports semantic interoperability, enhances data integration, and enables advanced flexibility and optimization services in practice.

Figure 3-13 diagram presents the application of the U2Demo Player module to Scenario 1 of the Dutch pilot, focusing on the key roles involved in day-ahead flexibility scheduling. It reuses core concepts from SEAS and ENERSHARE, and highlights the U2Demo-specific extensions such as the *u2d-play:HouseEnergyManagementSystem*, *u2d-play:GridEnergyManagementSystem*, *u2d-play:EnergyCommunityMember*, *u2d-play:EnergyCommunityManager*, and some ownership roles. These additions reflect the specific organisational structure and responsibilities of actors within the energy community, enabling semantic clarity and interoperability across scheduling, forecasting, and market operations.

Figure 3-13 – Dutch Pilot- Scenario 1 – Player Ontology

Next, Figure 3-14 diagram models the main semantic interactions between GEMS and HEMS in Scenario 1 of the Dutch pilot, where distributed flexibility assets are day-ahead scheduled based on forecasts, prices, and optimisation goals. The diagram demonstrates how the U2Demo ontology orchestrates these interactions across multiple layers: roles, assets, forecasts, schedules, and resulting time series profiles. It's important to highlight that these diagrams are not sequence diagrams and they just represent the interchanges between systems/processes according to the U2Demo ontology.

At the core, HEMS and GEMS are represented as subclasses of *ener-play:EnergyManagementSystem*, with *u2d-play:HouseEnergyManagementSystem* responsible for asset-level coordination and *u2d-play:GridEnergyManagementSystem* for aggregated community-level decision-making.

Each HEMS instance is associated with one or more flexibility assets (*u2d-dvc:FlexibilityAsset*), such as *seas:HeatPump*, *seas:SolarPanel*, *s4ener:Storage*, or *seas:ElectricVehicle*. These assets expose their operational state using the property *u2d-prop:StateProperty* and are evaluated for scheduling through optimisation events (*ener-evnt:OptimizationEvent*). The result of this process is a *u2d-evnt:HEMSScheduling* event, which specifies the scheduled operation of devices within a household. The GEMS computed internal price profile (*u2d-ts:EnergyCommunityInternalPriceProfile*) is also an important profile for the optimization. This profile guides local decision-making and internal trading by reflecting a dynamic price signal adapted to internal conditions, distinct from the wholesale market (*seas:DayAheadMarket*).

The outputs of HEMS scheduling are reflected in three key time series profiles:

1. *u2d-ts:ECMemberImportProfile*
2. *u2d-ts:ECMemberExportProfile*
3. *ic-flex:FlexibilityProfile*

These outputs capture the expected import/export behavior of the household, as well as the available flexibility to be aggregated by the GEMS.

At the community level, the GEMS uses several input forecasts (*s4ener:receives*) to compute the optimal internal price and aggregated schedule. Although the main inputs are the results of each individual HEMS scheduling within the community (*u2d-ts:ECMemberImportProfile*, *u2d-ts:ECMemberExportProfile* and *ic-flex:FlexibilityProfile*).

Based on these inputs, GEMS performs its own optimisation (*ener-evnt:OptimizationEvent*), producing a *u2d-evnt:GEMSScheduling* event and resulting in the export and import optimal results of each EC member that are sent to the HEMS of each of them following the updated *u2d-ts:ECMemberImportProfile* and *u2d-ts:ECMemberExportProfile*.

A computed internal price profile (*u2d-ts:EnergyCommunityInternalPriceProfile*) from GEMS provides a profile that guides local decision-making and internal trading by reflecting a dynamic price signal adapted to internal conditions, distinct from the wholesale market (*seas:DayAheadMarket*).

The other profiles that the GEMS receives are:

1. General forecasts of weather (*u2d-fc:ForecastOfWeather*) and market prices (*u2d-ts:MarketPriceProfile*) to contextualize decisions.

The GEMS is also responsible to store and produce the following forecasts profiles:

1. Aggregated forecasts at the community level, such as *u2d-fc:ForecastOfECPVProduction* and *u2d-fc:ForecastOfECConsumption*, which feed into *u2d-ts:ECPVProfile* and *u2d-ts:ECConsumptionProfile*.
2. Forecasts of individual members' PV production and consumption, e.g., *u2d-fc:ForecastOfECMemberPVProduction*, linked to *u2d-ts:ECMemberPVProfile* and *u2d-ts:ECMemberConsumptionProfile*.

The entire representation from device-level state evaluation, through local scheduling, to community-level aggregation and price generation is structured using the ontology's reusable modules, aligned with the description made in 3.2.1. The numeration that is found in the Figure 3-14 is aligned with the activity description from the IEC template for the 1st scenario of the Dutch pilot. The diagram also shows the repeated use of *saref:hasProfile*, *s4ener:receives*, and *saref:hasResult* to trace the dependencies and outputs of each event and forecast.

This model supports interoperable coordination between multiple HEMS and a single GEMS, enabling energy communities to operate as cohesive units while respecting individual asset constraints and market conditions.

Figure 3-14 – Dutch Pilot- Scenario 1

Next, we focus on the application of the ontology to the BOs of the Dutch Pilot- Scenario 1.

The Figure 3-15 diagram models the semantic structure for generating Energy Community Internal Energy Prices within GEMS in Scenario 1. It shows how the U2Demo ontology integrates with SAREF, SAREF4ENER, SEAS, and ENERSHARE to represent the service definition, required inputs, and structured output of the pricing process.

At the top level, *u2d-play:GridEnergyManagementSystem* exposes a service (*oneM2M:hasService*) modeled as *s4grid:GetService* with a specific instance ex:DefineECInternalPricesfromGEMS. This service contains an operation (*saref:hasOperation*), here ex:ECInternalEnergyPrices, which is the process that generates the internal pricing information.

The operation requires three main inputs (*saref:hasInput*):

1. *u2d-fc:ForecastOfPrice* – anticipated market or internal price signals.
2. *u2d-fc:ForecastOfECPVProduction* – expected PV generation within the energy community.
3. *u2d-fc:ForecastOfECConsumption* – expected energy consumption within the community.

The output (*saref:hasOutput*) is an *u2d-ts:EnergyCommunityInternalPriceProfile*, a U2Demo extension of *s4ener:TimeSeries*. This profile captures the internal price evolution over time, with each data point (*s4ener:DataPoint*) containing metadata such as update rate, temporal resolution, and measured value.

The price profile is linked to price properties (*seas:PriceProperty*) via ENERSHARE's and U2Demo properties ontology relationships (*ener-price:hasInternalPrice*, *u2d-price:hasBuyingPrice*, *u2d-price:hasSellingPrice*). Each price property is further specialised into *seas:BuyingPriceProperty*, *seas:SellingPriceProperty*, or the U2Demo-specific *u2d-price:InternalCommunityPrice*. All are associated with quantitative values (*saref:hasValue*) and units of measurement (*saref:isMeasuredIn*) using the EUR currency (*om2:euro*) from OM ontology and the value from XSD ontology, for example.

By modeling the full chain from service definition to time series output, this ontology representation ensures that internal price signals are semantically explicit, interoperable, and machine-readable, supporting their integration into community scheduling, market participation, and flexibility trading workflows.

Figure 3-15 – Dutch Pilot- Scenario 1 – Profiles of the exchanged information “Info 26 : EC internal energy prices”

BO “Scheduling information of a HEMS” (Info 27) profiles are presented in Figure 3-16, that details the semantic structure used to represent the scheduling results produced by a *u2d-play:HouseEnergyManagementSystem* (HEMS) within Scenario 1. The HEMS exposes its scheduling functionality through a *s4grid:GetService* (ex:HEMSScheduling) containing a *s4grid:GetOperation* (ex:IndividualLookAheadEnergyResourcesScheduling). This operation consumes three forecast inputs (*saref:hasInput*):

1. *u2d-ts:EnergyCommunityInternalPriceProfile* – the internal price signal computed at the community level;
2. *u2d-fc:ForecastOfECMemberPVProduction* – the member’s forecasted PV generation;
3. *u2d-fc:ForecastOfECMemberConsumption* – the member’s forecasted electricity demand.

The operation's output (*saref:hasOutput*) consists of three distinct time series profiles:

1. *ic-flex:FlexibilityProfile* – representing the temporal availability of controllable flexibility for the member;
2. *u2d-ts:ECMemberImportProfile* – the expected import from the community or grid;
3. *u2d-ts:ECMemberExportProfile* – the expected export to the community or grid.

Each of these profiles is modeled as an *s4ener:TimeSeries*, composed of multiple *s4ener:DataPoint* instances, with 15 minutes resolution. A data point includes core temporal and structural attributes such as *s4ener:hasUpdateRate*, *s4ener:hasTemporalResolution*, *s4ener:hasEffectivePeriod*, and *s4ener:hasCreationTime*.

Data points are semantically linked to *saref:EnergyAndPowerProperty*, which in turn is specialised into *ener-prop:ActivePowerProperty* and *ener-prop:ReactivePowerProperty*. For each property, the ontology captures:

- the computed/observed value (*saref:hasValue*) via a *saref:PropertyValue*;
- the timestamp of the measurement (*saref:hasTimestamp*);
- the unit of measure (*saref:isMeasuredIn*) following om2 (Ontology of units of Measure 2) definitions, that include *om2:Unit* e.g., watts (*om2:W*), volt-amperes (*om2:VA*) and unit prefixes (*om2:Prefix*) e.g., kilo (*om2:k*) or mega (*om2:M*) .

This representation guarantees that household-level scheduling outputs are unambiguous, temporally aligned, and expressed with consistent units, allowing them to be directly aggregated and processed by the GEMS for higher-level optimisation and flexibility management within the U2Demo framework.

Figure 3-16 – Dutch Pilot- Scenario 1 – Profiles of the exchanged information “Info 27 : Scheduling information of a HEMS”

The Figure 3-17 shows the diagram, which models the “Organize information about possible flexibility and the schedule” activity within the UC NL: Full operation of the Energy Community, part 01 – Day-Ahead Scheduling and Profile of the EC.

It shows how the GEMS, after completing the community-level optimization, schedules the import and export power profiles for each HEMS. This step also involves storing the optimization results to support market participation and communication with external stakeholders such as the DSO.

The output, “Info28: EC member Import/Export Scheduling”, is represented as a structured time series with:

- HEMS identifiers
- Timestamps for the schedule horizon (e.g., daily in 15-minute intervals)

- Scheduled active and reactive power values for power imported to and exported from each EC member
- Units (e.g., kW, kVAr) and measurement metadata

The ontology links the scheduling data to standardized concepts (SAREF, SEAS, OM) describing energy and power properties, their values, units, and temporal resolution, enabling consistent interpretation and exchange of scheduling information between the GEMS, individual HEMS controllers, and external market or grid actors.

Figure 3-17 – Dutch Pilot- Scenario 1 – Profiles of the exchanged information “Info28: EC member Import/Export Scheduling”

The Figure 3-18 shows the diagram, which models the “PV production and consumption forecast” activity within the same Dutch UC.

It shows how the GEMS uses one-HEMS forecasting services to process multiple inputs — numerical weather forecasts, generation profiles, and EC member consumption profiles — to produce time-series forecasts for the PV production and consumption of **each individual household (HEMS)** in the energy community.

The output, “Info29: Forecast information for the GEMS”, is represented as a structured time series with:

- HEMS identifiers
- Timestamps for the forecast horizon (e.g., daily in 15-minute intervals)
- Forecasted active and reactive power values (PV production and consumption)
- Units (e.g., kW, kVAr) and measurement metadata

The ontology links the forecast data to standardized concepts (SAREF, SEAS, OM) describing energy and power properties, their values, units, and temporal resolution, enabling consistent interpretation and exchange of forecast information across systems.

Figure 3-18 – Dutch Pilot- Scenario 1 – Profiles of the exchanged information “Info29: Forecast information for the GEMS”

The Figure 3-19 shows the diagram, which models the “PV production and consumption forecast” activity within the UC NL: Full operation of the Energy Community, part 01 – Day-Ahead Scheduling and Profile of the EC.

It shows how the GEMS uses aggregated HEMS forecasting services to process multiple inputs (numerical weather forecasts, generation profiles, and EC member consumption profiles) to produce time-series forecasts for the PV production and consumption of the **whole energy community**.

The output, “Info30: Forecast information for the GEMS”, is represented as a structured time series with:

- Timestamps for the forecast horizon (e.g., daily in 15-minute intervals)
- Forecasted active and reactive power values (PV production and consumption)
- Units (e.g., kW, kVAr) and measurement metadata

The ontology links the forecast data to standardized concepts (SAREF, SEAS, OM) describing energy and power properties, their values, units, and temporal resolution, enabling consistent interpretation and exchange of forecast information across systems.

Figure 3-19 – Dutch Pilot- Scenario 1 – Profiles of the exchanged information “Info30: Forecast information for the GEMS”

3.2.4 Next Steps

With the conceptual design of the U2Demo ontology defined and validated through its application to Scenario 1 of the Dutch pilot, the next phase is to move from conceptual modeling presented in this deliverable to a formal implementation that is machine-readable, interoperable, and ready for integration into pilot systems and in the U2Demo Platform. This will begin with encoding the ontology in a standard representation such as OWL 2 (Web Ontology Language) or RDF/Turtle (TTL), ensuring compliance with W3C Semantic Web recommendations. In this process, the class and concepts hierarchies defined in this deliverable will be implemented as *rdfs:Class* and *owl:Class* entities, while relationships and attributes will be expressed as *owl:ObjectProperty* and *owl:DatatypeProperty* elements, complete with domain and range constraints to preserve semantic integrity. The implementation will also formalize alignments to existing ontologies such as SAREF, SEAS, and ENERSHARE through equivalence and subclass relations, thereby maximising reuse and ensuring interoperability, as presented in this section. Each concept and property will be annotated with human-readable labels, comments, and definitions to support both comprehension and maintainability. In essence, this phase corresponds to the serialization of the each of the U2Demo ontological modules presented in this deliverable.

Once the formal ontology is completed, it will be published under a persistent URI namespace with proper version management, allowing partners and stakeholders to access and reuse the authoritative version (e.g., in a public Git repository), as suggested in the step 6 of the methodology to create the U2Demo ontology (Figure 3-1). Building on this core, specific data models can be created for each pilot use case. These models will select the relevant ontology concepts, constrain them for the scenario, and potentially define validation rules using technologies such as SHACL (SHACL has been designed to enhance the semantic and technical interoperability layers of ontologies expressed as RDF graphs). They will also specify how the ontology is serialized for data exchange, for example in JSON-LD to be used in APIs and will map these semantic elements to the actual data fields present in the pilots' datasets. This mapping will ensure that the ontology is not an abstract layer but a direct semantic reference for the real data exchanged in the project. The approach can be top-down, starting from the U2Demo ontology and taking steps towards creating use case specific API specifications and schemas or a bottom-up starting from their use case specific data sample or schema and taking steps towards the U2Demo ontology modules.

To illustrate this process, we return to Scenario 1 of the Dutch Pilot and focus on the business object (BO) "EC Internal Energy Prices" as represented in Figure 3-15. The first example below shows a JSON-LD serialization aligned with the U2Demo ontology, making explicit the class, property, and relationship definitions, as well as their mappings to external ontologies such as SAREF, SAREF4ENER, SEAS, and ENERSHARE. It is important to note that the namespace prefixes and URIs used in the JSON-LD example (e.g., "u2d-ts": "http://u2demo.eu/ontology/timeseries#") are illustrative only, as the U2Demo ontology has not yet been published. Once the ontology is made available, these URIs will need to be replaced with the final persistent and resolvable namespace addresses.

```
{
  "@context": {
    "u2d-ts": "http://u2demo.eu/ontology/timeseries#",
    "u2d-fc": "http://u2demo.eu/ontology/forecast#",
    "u2d-price": "http://u2demo.eu/ontology/price#",
    "ener-price": "http://enershare.eu/ontology/price#",
    "s4ener": "https://saref.etsi.org/saref4ener#",
    "s4grid": "https://saref.etsi.org/saref4grid#",
```

```

"saref": "https://saref.etsi.org/core#",
"seas": "https://w3id.org/seas/",
"om2": "http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/",
"xsd": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#"
},
"@id": "http://u2demo.eu/data/priceprofiles/ECInternalPriceProfile_2025-08-08",
"@type": "u2d-ts:EnergyCommunityInternalPriceProfile",
"rdfs:subClassOf": "s4ener:TimeSeries",
"s4ener:hasDataPoint": [
  {
    "@id": "http://u2demo.eu/data/datapoints/DP1",
    "@type": "s4ener:DataPoint",
    "s4ener:hasEffectivePeriod": {
      "start": "2025-08-08T00:00:00Z",
      "end": "2025-08-08T01:00:00Z"
    },
    "s4ener:hasCreationTime": "2025-08-07T12:00:00Z",
    "ener-price:hasInternalPrice": {
      "@type": "u2d-price:InternalCommunityPrice",
      "saref:hasValue": {
        "@type": "saref:PropertyValue",
        "saref:hasValue": {
          "@value": 0.145,
          "@type": "xsd:decimal"
        }
      },
      "saref:isMeasuredIn": "om2:euro"
    }
  },
  {
    "u2d-price:hasBuyingPrice": {
      "@type": "seas:BuyingPriceProperty",
      "saref:hasValue": {
        "@value": 0.152,
        "@type": "xsd:decimal"
      },
      "saref:isMeasuredIn": "om2:euro"
    },
    "u2d-price:hasSellingPrice": {
      "@type": "seas:SellingPriceProperty",
      "saref:hasValue": {
        "@value": 0.138,
        "@type": "xsd:decimal"
      },
      "saref:isMeasuredIn": "om2:euro"
    }
  }
],
"saref:hasProfile": "u2d-fc:ForecastOfPrice"
}

```

While the JSON-LD form is ideal for semantic web environments and enables reasoning over the data, in many operational contexts a API-friendly data model representation is preferable. The second example shows a simplified JSON payload that still aligns with the ontology's concepts but is structured for easier integration into APIs or other application-level data exchanges that might be used in the U2Demo platform.

```
{
  "profileId": "ECInternalPriceProfile_2025-08-08",
  "profileType": "EnergyCommunityInternalPriceProfile",
  "creationTime": "2025-08-07T12:00:00Z",
  "dataPoints": [
    {
      "startTime": "2025-08-08T00:00:00Z",
      "endTime": "2025-08-08T01:00:00Z",
      "internalPriceEUR": 0.145,
      "buyingPriceEUR": 0.152,
      "sellingPriceEUR": 0.138
    },
    {
      "startTime": "2025-08-08T01:00:00Z",
      "endTime": "2025-08-08T02:00:00Z",
      "internalPriceEUR": 0.148,
      "buyingPriceEUR": 0.155,
      "sellingPriceEUR": 0.140
    }
  ],
  "sourceForecast": "ForecastOfPrice_2025-08-07"
}
```

The resulting ontology-driven data models will be integrated into the U2Demo semantic interoperability layer, where they will undergo validation against pilot data. This phase will include testing reasoning behaviour, checking conformance with the defined validation rules, and refining the ontology where necessary to close any gaps between the conceptual definitions and operational requirements. Once these iterations are complete, the ontology and its associated data models will be deployed and tested for each pilot. In doing so, they will enable consistent semantic interpretation across partners, facilitate cross-pilot data sharing, and support advanced analytics and automated decision-making, demonstrating the operational value of the U2Demo semantic framework in real-world energy community scenarios.

4 Interoperability Analysis

Interoperability is a core enabler for the U2Demo platform, ensuring that diverse systems, data models, and technical infrastructures across the four pilot sites can operate as a cohesive whole. Given the project's focus on P2P energy sharing, flexibility management, and integration with heterogeneous assets and platforms, the ability to exchange, interpret, and act on data consistently is fundamental to both operational performance and replicability.

The Interoperable Europe Act [42], which entered into force in April 2024, reinforces this ambition at the European level. By mandating the promotion of open standards and common interoperability frameworks, the Act aims to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of public services, stimulate economic growth, and foster innovation. Although primarily targeted at public sector digital transformation, its principles are directly relevant to U2Demo's objectives. The alignment of U2Demo's interoperability framework with these principles supports not only compliance with EU best practices but also the scalability of its solutions beyond the scope of the pilots.

In this section, the interoperability analysis examines the technical mechanisms required for seamless integration across pilots, external platforms, and supporting services. It identifies how U2Demo leverages open standards, middleware, and data formats to bridge diverse infrastructures, while ensuring secure and reliable data exchange in line with emerging European interoperability policies and frameworks.

4.1 Defining Interoperability Interfaces for U2Demo Platform

The definition of interoperability interfaces in U2Demo builds directly on the semantic ontology described in Section 3, ensuring that all data exchanges are both technically compatible and semantically meaningful. Each interface will be specified against the U2Demo ontology modules, so that concepts such as community roles, flexibility assets, price signals, or scheduling events are consistently represented across heterogeneous pilot systems. This ontology-driven approach provides a machine-readable contract for information exchange, allowing APIs and middleware connectors to map pilot-specific data models into a harmonized representation. The interoperability interfaces will therefore act as the operational layer of the ontology: they will define the message structures, payload formats, and binding protocols (REST, WebSockets, MQTT) while preserving semantic integrity. By grounding interface definitions in the ontology, U2Demo ensures that integration with Simpl Middleware, EW Digital Spine, and other external frameworks can occur without semantic loss, enabling scalable replication across energy communities and European data spaces.

4.2 Simpl Middleware Integration Considerations

This section describes the procedure and technical requirements for integrating an external service with the Simpl Middleware within the scope of interoperability pilots such as the U2Demo project. The objective is to ensure seamless, secure, and robust data exchange between the external service and the Simpl Middleware without requiring exposure of the internal logic of the service to be integrated (black-box concept).

4.2.1 Simpl Middleware Overview

The Simpl Middleware [8] acts as an interoperability layer enabling different platforms, services and data spaces to exchange data in a harmonized and uniform way using standard

communication protocols (REST, MQTT) and data formats (JSON, CIM/XML where applicable). It supports:

- Real-time and near-real-time data ingestion.
- Control commands and event notification delivery.
- Authorization and authentication via tokens or OAuth2.
- Monitoring and logging of data exchanges for traceability.
- Data publication, where the service publishes data (e.g. measurements, status updates).

4.2.2 Black-Box Service Overview

The black-box service will act as a data producer and/or consumer, interacting with Simpl via its public APIs. The internal logic of the service for this example is not considered, meaning that for this example the internal logic and use cases already defined for the U2Demo are not being taken into consideration, but rather a general integration is being defined; this integration focuses solely on:

- Input: Receiving commands or data queries from Simpl.
- Output: Sending measurements, status reports, or event notifications to Simpl.
- Registration: Allowing registration of users, entities and access to connectors.

4.2.3 Service Preparation

The first step towards a successful integration with Simpl Middleware is ensuring that the service being integrated meets all necessary technical requirements to leverage Simpl's functionalities securely and reliably. For this purpose, the following conditions must be fulfilled:

- The service must be able to make RESTful calls by using:
 - POST to send data to Simpl (e.g., measurements, status updates, events).
 - GET to receive data from Simpl (e.g., control commands, health status).
- The service must support mTLS:
 - The service must store and use client certificates and private keys securely.
 - It must store and trust the CA certificate used by Simpl to validate the server's identity.
- Given that Simpl uses OpenID Connect (OAuth2) for tier 1 credentials:
 - The service must support the OAuth2 Client Credentials Flow.
 - It must store, request, and automatically renew access_token values, handling token expiry gracefully.
 - Include the **Authorization: Bearer <token>** header in each request.
- JSON Data Handling:
 - The service must prepare and send JSON requests in the expected formats as defined by Simpl.
 - It must be capable of parsing and interpreting JSON responses received from Simpl.
 - Optionally, the service should validate outgoing payloads against a JSON Schema to catch errors before sending.
- The service must be able to do time management:
 - Be able to generate timestamps in Coordinated Universal Time (UTC), in ISO 8601 (example: 2025-07-03T13:00:00Z).

- It should ensure accurate and consistent temporal precision of all data being sent.

Besides the necessary technical requirements, some additional technical capabilities were considered a nice to have, albeit not completely necessary:

- Connectivity and resilience:
 - Implement automatic retries in case of connectivity failures or server errors.
 - Implement a data buffering mechanism to store unsent data locally during extended connectivity issues, ensuring no data loss.
 - Ensure correct handling of HTTP status codes.
- Logging and Monitoring:
 - The service should generate structured logs (preferably in JSON) including:
 - Timestamps, request endpoints, payloads, responses, status codes, and error details.
 - Integrate health checks using **GET /health** or equivalent before sending large batches of data.
 - Optionally, logs may be forwarded to centralized logging systems (e.g., Loki, Elastic) for pilot monitoring and debugging.
- Security and Policies:
 - Ensure all payloads and inputs are sanitized and validated to prevent injection attacks.
 - If Simpl applies Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC), the service must be able to include any required headers (e.g., x-participant-id, x-ecosystem-id).

4.2.4 Integration Scenarios

Simpl is being integrated alongside a Data Space (DS), where the DS owner must integrate an open-source, multi-vendor, large-scale, modular, and interoperable middleware called "Simpl-Open".

Simpl-Open enables the operation and interconnection within and between European data spaces, facilitating secure user migration to the cloud, while federating data, applications, and infrastructure across the EU with secure, resilient, energy-efficient, and accessible cloud-to-edge capabilities.

While the selected DS will have Simpl-Open's core components (including the Governance Agent) integrated by the dataspace operator, each participant within the U2Demo project must also integrate two additional agents:

- Consumer Agent, who:
 - Finds and negotiates data/services in the dataspace.
 - Establishes usage of contracts with providers.
 - Handles secure data retrieval under the agreed policies.
 - Logs into your organization's consumption activity.
- Producer Agent, who:
 - Publish datasets/services to the federated catalogue.
 - Defines usage policies and pricing (if applicable).
 - Responds to contract requests from consumers.

- Provides data access endpoints to consumers under contract.
- Logs who access your data/services.

While the Governance agent should be like the referee and organizer of the dataspace, having the following responsibilities:

Establishes trust: issues and verifies identities/credentials for participants.

Defines and enforces policies: how data can be accessed and shared.

Maintains the federated catalogue: where providers register datasets/services, and consumers discover them.

Audits activity: logs who accesses what, ensuring compliance.

Manages onboarding: accepts/rejects participants.

Meaning that it does not provide or consume data itself, but rather it ensures rules, trust and secure coordination between participants. This agent should be operated by the dataspace owner/operator.

There are three scenarios currently considered viable regarding the integration of a service with Simpl Middleware:

Scenario 1:

A selected Data Space (DS) to be utilized within the U2Demo project is already integrated with a Governance Agent, indicating it is ready for connection and secure data exchange. In this case, it is necessary to contact the DS owner to align on the API endpoints and authentication methods to be used for integration. However, the required endpoints (e.g., authentication, contract negotiation, data retrieval) should already be available within the DS, facilitating a faster onboarding and integration process for the project.

Participants may also need to complete onboarding procedures with the DS's Governance Agent to receive the necessary credentials for authentication and policy enforcement. An alignment regarding contractual terms and data usage policies may also be required prior to initiating data exchanges.

Each U2Demo participant will still need to:

- Deploy their Consumer Agent to discover, negotiate, and consume data/services from the DS.
- Deploy their Producer Agent if they intend to offer data/services within the DS.
- Complete onboarding with the newly deployed Governance Agent, receiving the necessary credentials for secure authentication and policy compliance.

Scenario 2:

A selected Data Space (DS) to be utilized within the U2Demo project does not yet have Simpl-Open integrated. In this case, the DS owner will need to integrate the Simpl-Open middleware stack to enable secure, interoperable data exchange within the dataspace and across other European data spaces.

The integration of Simpl-Open by the DS owner involves:

- Deploying and configuring the Simpl-Open Agent stack, including the Governance Agent for trust and onboarding management.
- Setting up catalogue services for participants to publish and discover datasets and services.

- Configuring contract negotiation, authentication, and data transfer endpoints.
- Aligning on vocabularies, data models, and policy enforcement mechanisms to ensure interoperability with U2Demo.

While the DS owner is responsible for deploying Simpl-Open, each U2Demo participant will still need to:

- Deploy their Consumer Agent to discover, negotiate, and consume data/services from the DS once Simpl-Open is operational.
- Deploy their Producer Agent if they intend to offer data/services within the DS.
- Complete onboarding with the newly deployed Governance Agent, receiving the necessary credentials for secure authentication and policy compliance.

This scenario will require additional coordination with the DS owner to plan and track the Simpl-Open deployment timeline to align with U2Demo's project milestones.

Scenario 3:

In this scenario, the U2Demo project itself would create and operate its own Data Space (DS) to support project-specific needs for data exchange and service orchestration among consortium partners.

This scenario, while possible, is considered improbable due to the significant effort, resources, and governance structures required. However, it may be relevant if no suitable DS exists for the targeted use cases or if strict control over the DS environment is necessary for regulatory, security, or testing reasons.

Establishing a U2Demo-owned DS would require:

- Deployment and operation of the Simpl-Open middleware stack by the U2Demo consortium, including:
 - Governance Agent to manage participant onboarding, trust frameworks, credential issuance, and policy enforcement.
 - Catalogue services to enable publishing and discovery of datasets and services.
 - Contract negotiation, authentication, and data transfer endpoints.
 - Defining and enforcing data governance policies, vocabularies, and shared data models within the consortium.
 - Setting up infrastructure (cloud or on-premises) capable of supporting the Simpl-Open agents and associated services reliably throughout the project lifetime.
 - Ensuring compliance with security, privacy, and data sovereignty requirements applicable within the EU and across the project partners' jurisdictions.

Even if U2Demo operates its own DS, each project participant will still need to:

- Deploy their Consumer Agent to discover, negotiate, and consume data/services within the DS.
- Deploy their Producer Agent if they intend to offer data/services within the DS.
- Complete onboarding and credential configuration with the U2Demo-operated Governance Agent to participate securely in the dataspace.
- Prior to activating the DS, the consortium should:

- Align on API structures, governance procedures, and usage policies.
- Develop a deployment, testing, and maintenance plan for the Simpl-Open stack.
- Allocate resources for ongoing operational management and support.

While this scenario provides maximum control and customization for U2Demo, it requires significant coordination, technical expertise, and operational commitment from the consortium.

A note must be made that these three scenarios are **not** mutually exclusive, but rather, they can all be applied at the same time if it makes sense to do so. If what makes sense is to create a Data Space (Scenario 3), we'll still be able to connect with already existing DS who already have Simpl integrated (Scenario 1) or communicate and align with DS owners who might still not have this integration made (Scenario 2).

4.2.5 Communication Interfaces

REST Endpoints Provided by Simpl:

For effective integration, the following endpoints are identified as essential:

- Consumption (Consumer Agent):
 - GET /catalog – Discover available datasets/services.
 - POST /catalog/request – Query catalogue with advanced filters.
 - POST /management/v3/contractnegotiations – Initiate contract negotiation for an asset.
 - GET /management/v3/contractnegotiations/{id} – Check negotiation status.
 - GET /management/v3/contractagreements – List active agreements.
 - POST /management/v3/transferprocesses – Initiate a transfer process to consume data/services.
 - GET /management/v3/transferprocesses/{id} – Check transfer status.
 - POST /management/v3/transferprocesses/{id}/terminate – Terminate a transfer process.
- Production (Producer Agent):
 - POST /management/v3/assets – Register and publish datasets/services.
 - GET /management/v3/assets/{id} – Retrieve asset details.
 - DELETE /management/v3/assets/{id} – Unpublish assets.
 - GET /management/v3/contractnegotiations – List contract negotiations from consumers.
 - GET /management/v3/transferprocesses – Monitor active consumption requests.

These endpoints collectively enable the U2Demo project to discover, negotiate, consume, and offer data/services within Simpl-Open-enabled Data Spaces under clear, contract-based, and secure processes.

- Measurements and status uploads:

- POST /measurements - for uploading measurements or sensor data.
- POST /status - for sending status updates of devices and availability.
- POST /events - for sending event notifications (failures, flexibility events, etc.)
- Monitoring:
 - GET /health or /status - for monitoring the availability of Simpl.

Payload Format: JSON with the following structure (example for measurements):

```
{
  "device_id": "device_12345",
  "timestamp": "2025-07-03T13:00:00Z",
  "measurements": {
    "active_power": 1200,
    "reactive_power": 300
  }
}
```

4.2.6 Simpl Middleware and U2Demo

At the current stage of the U2Demo project, the technical scope and configuration are not yet fully defined. As such, while the general integration approach with Simpl Middleware is understood and documented in this guide, some key elements required for implementation are still pending clarification.

These include:

- The final list of endpoints that will be exposed by the Simpl instance in the U2Demo project.
- The authentication model to be used (OAuth2, mTLS, or a combination).
- The rate limits, payload frequency and size constraints applicable to this deployment.
- The extent to which Gaia-X self-descriptions and service onboarding will be required or optional.

Because of these uncertainties, the detailed integration steps provided in this document must be seen as a general technical reference — they are not yet fully validated against the final deployment setup of the Simpl instance for U2Demo.

4.3 API Requirements and Data Exchange Formats

4.3.1 EW Digital Spine Client

The EW Digital Spine [43] Client offers both RESTful and WSS APIs to interact with the data exchange platform. The contents of this section provide details of these APIs and the formats supported by the EW Digital Spine platform.

4.3.2 EW Digital Spine Client RESTful APIs

The EW Digital Spine Client provides RESTful APIs for enterprise systems to integrate with. These covers below modules:

- Authentication – APIs to authenticate end users with basic authentication, and enterprise systems with API Keys
- End User Management – APIs to manage end users of the EW Digital Spine Client UI
- API Key Management – APIs to manage API Keys to be used by enterprise systems for authenticated system-to-system integration with the EW Digital Spine Client
- Enterprise User Management – APIs to set the private key of the enterprise user, request verifiable credentials (roles), and publish approved VCs to its respective Decentralized Identifier (DID) document
- Association Keys Management – APIs to manage association keys of the enterprise user to anonymize its identity
- Client Gateway Management – these APIs are used to set the mTLS certificates of the client to the message broker for transport layer security, and to monitor the client gateway's health such as connection with the message broker, the database, and scheduled jobs
- Applications Management – set of APIs to retrieve details of applications which the enterprise user has access to
- Topics Management – APIs to manage data schemas that passes through the data exchange platform provided that the enterprise user possesses the required roles to perform such actions
- Message Channels Management – APIs to group topics and specify in what manner data are sent to and received from
- Address Book – enables the enterprise user to easily associate a DID with a human-readable name
- Messaging (Data Exchange) - APIs to exchange messages such as plain JSON data or files
- Message Stream Clients Management – APIs to manage the limited amount of client slots that can read a stream of messages based on channel configurations

4.3.3 EW Digital Spine Client WSS APIs

The EW Digital Spine Client WSS APIs are mainly used to send and receive messages using Web Sockets. These APIs only covers the Messaging (Data Exchange) module and does not include all other modules as described in the RESTful APIs.

4.3.4 Data Exchange Formats

The EW Digital Spine supports below data formats:

- Basic Data Exchange – plain JSON Object based on JSD-7 specifications
- File Transfer – JSON, CSV, TSV, XML

5 Cybersecurity and Data Privacy Considerations

As peer-to-peer (P2P) trading and energy sharing systems gain traction across Europe, ensuring cybersecurity and data privacy becomes paramount. These decentralized platforms depend on trust, secure communication, and protection of sensitive user and system data. This document outlines the cybersecurity strategy for the project, focusing on two core areas: the assessment of cyber risks specific to P2P energy environments, and the design and implementation of a robust security framework covering authentication, encryption, and access control. The strategy is aligned with key regulatory frameworks, including the NIS 2 Directive [14] and the forthcoming Network Code on Cybersecurity (NCCS) [15], and adheres to international standards to support scalable, secure, and interoperable energy ecosystems.

5.1 Cybersecurity Risk Assessment for P2P Trading and Energy Sharing

The decentralized and data-intensive nature of peer-to-peer (P2P) trading and energy sharing introduces a complex cybersecurity landscape. Ensuring Trust, availability, and confidentiality of energy data and trading mechanisms is essential for protecting participants and infrastructure. This is particularly important as the platform is designed to operate across different Energy Communities (ECs) with varying regulatory environments, governance models, and technological maturity.

The cybersecurity risk assessment strategy includes:

- **Threat Modeling and Risk Analysis:** Identification of potential attack vectors such as Sybil attacks, smart contract exploits, data manipulation, unauthorized access, and denial-of-service attacks across distributed components, including blockchain nodes, smart meters, APIs, edge devices, and user interfaces.
- **Standards-Based Assessment:** Application of internationally recognized methodologies aligned with ISO/IEC 27005 [44], NIST SP 800-39 [45], and ISO 31000 [46] for identifying, evaluating, and mitigating risks. These standards ensure a structured approach to understanding vulnerabilities, threat likelihood, and impact severity.
- **Energy System-Specific Frameworks:** Integration of NISTIR 7628 [12], [47] and IEC 62443 series [10], [11] provides tailored cybersecurity controls for decentralized energy environments. These frameworks address the unique risks posed by interconnected energy systems, including physical attacks on infrastructure, data injection attacks, and command spoofing.
- **Contextual Adaptation:** Each of the four Energy Community (EC) pilots will undergo individual risk profiling to capture the specific cybersecurity needs and challenges of their operational context. Factors such as DER penetration, local policy, and user engagement models will inform the risk management approach.
- **Incident Response and Monitoring:** Establishment of advanced security monitoring systems, intrusion detection mechanisms, and automated alerting capabilities to support proactive incident detection. Response protocols will follow ENISA guidelines

[48] and align with requirements outlined in the forthcoming EU Network Code on Cybersecurity (NCCS) [15], facilitating timely mitigation and recovery.

- **Regulatory Alignment:** The risk assessment framework is designed to support compliance with the NIS 2 Directive and NCCS, ensuring readiness for mandatory incident reporting, audit trails, and supply chain risk management as dictated by EU legislation.

This risk-based approach ensures dynamic adaptability and fosters trust among participants by addressing security concerns proactively and comprehensively.

5.2 Security Framework (Authentication, Encryption and Access Control)

This framework is supported by a set of internationally recognized cybersecurity standards and guidelines relevant to both IT systems and operational environments in the energy sector. Key standards and frameworks applicable to this project include:

- **ISO/IEC 27001:** Information Security Management System (ISMS) standard used to structure organizational security policies and ensure continuous risk management.
- **ISO/IEC 27005:** Provides guidelines for information security risk management within the ISMS framework.
- **ISO/IEC 27019:** Extends ISO 27002 for information security management specifically to energy utility environments.
- **NIST SP 800-53 & SP 800-82:** Provide security and privacy controls for federal information systems and specific guidance for Industrial Control Systems.
- **NISTIR 7628:** Tailored guidance for energy systems that identifies functional domains and defines cybersecurity controls and impact assessments.
- **IEC 62443 series:** Provides security for industrial automation and control systems, with emphasis on system security requirements (IEC 62443-3-3), product security (IEC 62443-4-1/4-2), and roles/responsibilities (IEC 62443-2-1).
- **IEC 62351:** Specifies data and communication security measures for power system information exchange, applicable to energy-specific protocols.
- **ENISA Guidelines:** Offers EU-specific guidance on cybersecurity for energy operators, with recommendations for threat identification, vulnerability management, and incident response.
- **EU Network Code on Cybersecurity (NCCS):** The emerging regulatory framework defining minimum cybersecurity requirements, risk assessment responsibilities, and cross-border coordination mechanisms for electricity sector stakeholders.

These standards collectively ensure that the platform architecture, governance models, and security implementations meet rigorous expectations for resilience, trust, and regulatory compliance across diverse energy communities.

The platform's security framework is grounded in a multilayered defence model that aligns with both IT and operational technology (OT) cybersecurity standards relevant to the European energy sector. It aims to create a secure, interoperable, and scalable infrastructure where participants can trade energy securely and confidently.

- **Authentication:**

- Implementation of strong identity verification mechanisms using decentralized identifiers (DIDs), public key infrastructure (PKI), and multi-factor authentication (MFA). This ensures only verified users and devices can interact with the platform.
- Device authentication is enforced through secure protocols and digital certificates compliant with IEC 62443-4-2 and IEC 62351, which define cybersecurity requirements for energy devices and secure communication.
- Smart contracts will be bound to cryptographically signed identities, providing transparency and non-repudiation of transactions.

- **Encryption:**

- All communications within the platform will be encrypted using state-of-the-art protocols such as TLS 1.3, ensuring data integrity and confidentiality during transmission.
- Sensitive data stored on-chain or off-chain will be encrypted using AES-256 or similarly strong algorithms.

- **Access Control:**

- Implementation of Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) and Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) ensures that access to system functions, data, and trading interfaces is granted based on user roles and contextual attributes.
- Access control policies will be enforced through programmable smart contracts, reducing human error and enabling automated permission checks.
- System-level access and administrative operations will follow ISO/IEC 27001 principles and IEC 62443-3-3 controls, ensuring full traceability and accountability.

- **Audit and Logging:**

- All user actions, data access events, and system-level operations will be logged and secured in compliance with ISO 27001 and IEC 62351-100 standards.

Blockchain-based tamper-evident logs may be used to ensure data integrity and traceability.

- **Data Privacy Compliance:**
 - User consent and data usage transparency will be integrated into the platform, ensuring compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Data minimization and purpose limitation principles will be enforced by design.

The security framework will be rigorously tested and validated through four diverse Energy Community pilots, each reflecting unique governance structures and technology adoption. The framework is designed to evolve with emerging threats and regulatory developments, establishing a replicable cybersecurity model for the wider energy sector.

5.3 Confidential Computing

5.3.1 Overview of Confidential Computing in Energy Data Platforms

This energy data platforms process highly sensitive information such as:

- Real-time consumption and production profiles.
- Trade bids and offers.
- Grid utilization factors from DSOs/TSOs.
- Fairness and energy poverty indicators.

While encryption protects data at rest and in transit, it does not safeguard data in use during computation. This leaves a gap where sensitive inputs can be exposed to unauthorized access, including malicious insiders or compromised cloud systems. Confidential computing addresses this vulnerability by ensuring computations occur in isolated, verifiable environments or through cryptographic methods that prevent exposure of raw data.

Core Techniques in Confidential Computing:

1. Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs):

A Trusted Execution Environment is a secure hardware-based enclave that ensures authenticity, confidentiality, and integrity of code and data during execution, even if the underlying operating system or hypervisor is compromised.

Key capabilities include:

- **Authenticity & Confidentiality** of code and data inside the enclave.
- **State Integrity:** Protection of memory, Central Processing Unit (CPU) registers, and I/O from tampering.

- **Dynamic Updates:** Secure updates to the enclave's contents during execution.
- **Attestation:** Verifiable proof to third parties that computations ran inside a trusted environment.
- **Example:** Intel SGX enclaves enable secure remote computation with strong protection against both software and hardware attacks.

2. Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC):

SMPC allows multiple parties to jointly compute a function over their inputs without revealing those inputs to each other.

Workflow:

- **Input Encryption:** Each participant encrypts their private data.
- **Distributed Computation:** Encrypted inputs are processed collaboratively without exposing the raw values.
- **Result Aggregation:** Partial outputs are combined securely.
- **Result Decryption:** Final results are decrypted without revealing any party's individual input.
- **Output Delivery:** The securely computed output is delivered without tampering.

3. Privacy-Preserving Application Patterns:

Combining TEEs, SMPC, and blockchain enables privacy-preserving workflows tailored to energy data platforms:

- **Secure Trade Matching:** Protects bids and offers until a match is finalized, preventing competitive intelligence leaks.
- **Privacy-Preserving Demand Response:** Runs optimization algorithms for load shifting without exposing individual household profiles.
- **Operator Coordination:** Facilitates private data exchange between DSOs and TSOs, ensuring grid utilization metrics are aggregated and privacy-verified.
- **Fairness & Social Equality Module:** Computes energy poverty indicators and fairness scoring without revealing participant identities.
- **Confidential Business Model Evaluation:** Simulates new tariffs and P2P pricing models without leaking sensitive market data.

4. Benefits for Energy Data Platforms:

- **Data Privacy:** Protects all stages of computation from unauthorized access.
- **Trustworthiness:** Even infrastructure and cloud operators cannot see raw data.

- **Regulatory Compliance:** Aligns with GDPR, the EU Data Governance Act, and sector-specific privacy rules.
- **Blockchain Synergy:** When paired with blockchain (e.g., Energy Web), confidential computing ensures tamper-proof results and auditable attestations without exposing sensitive inputs.

5.3.2 Potential Applications in U2Demo

This project focuses on P2P trading and energy sharing in Energy Communities (ECs), supported by the Energy Web blockchain for transparency, interoperability, and trust. Four pilot implementations will test different governance models, market coordination mechanisms, and fairness metrics. To ensure privacy and trust in all operations, confidential computing will be integrated into the data processing layer.

Use Cases in the Project:

Secure Trade Matching in TEEs

Bid and offer data from prosumers will be processed inside TEEs, ensuring no premature disclosure of competitive information.

Demand Response Optimization via SMPC

Multiple stakeholders will collaboratively calculate load-shifting strategies without revealing individual consumption patterns.

- **Secure Operator Coordination**

DSOs and TSOs will exchange and analyse grid usage metrics in privacy-preserving environments.

- **Fairness Analytics in TEEs**

Compute social fairness metrics and energy poverty indicators while keeping personal identities hidden.

- **Confidential Business Model Simulation**

Test new tariff models and pricing mechanisms without leaking sensitive strategic data.

6 Conclusions

6.1 Summary

The work performed in Task T3.2 has provided U2Demo with a solid technical foundation for standardization, interoperability, and cybersecurity, enabling the design of a robust, scalable, and secure platform for peer-to-peer (P2P) energy sharing. The activities combined a systematic partner capability assessment, an agile methodology for semantic model development, and a comprehensive security and privacy framework aligned with EU requirements.

On the semantic interoperability front, a six-step agile ontology development methodology, adapted from the AIME approach used in European Data Space projects, was applied to the U2Demo context. The process began with a detailed extraction of concepts, actors, and business objects (BOs) from the 10 Business Use Cases (BUCs) defined in Task 1.4. This ensured the ontology design was driven by real operational needs and covered the full lifecycle of EC operations, from day-ahead scheduling to market settlement and flexibility activation. Existing ontologies such as SAREF (and its SAREF4ENER, SAREF4BLDG, SAREF4GRID extensions), SEAS, and ENERSHARE were reviewed for reusable components. Gaps were identified through mapping and gap analysis, leading to the introduction of U2Demo-specific modules covering concepts absent in current standards, such as:

- Internal Community Price profiles and flexibility-related price properties.
- Roles and responsibilities specific to EC governance (e.g., Energy Community Manager, Grid Energy Management System).
- Event taxonomies for optimization, activation, and evaluation processes.
- Domain-specific forecast and schedule structures at both household and community levels.

The ontology was organized into 10 interoperable core modules (System, Player, Market, Forecast, TimeSeries, Schedule, Device, Event, Price, and Properties) each aligned with existing standards where possible and extended where necessary. This modular approach ensures scalability, maintainability, and reusability across pilots, while enabling semantic consistency between heterogeneous partner systems.

From a cybersecurity perspective, the deliverable established a multi-layered security framework grounded in internationally recognized standards (ISO/IEC 27001, ISO/IEC 27019, IEC 62443, NISTIR 7628) and fully aligned with GDPR, the NIS 2 Directive, and the forthcoming EU Network Code on Cybersecurity (NCCS). The framework addresses the uneven maturity levels observed among partners, providing a harmonized baseline that includes:

- Strong authentication mechanisms, combining decentralized identifiers (DIDs), PKI-based device certificates, and multi-factor authentication (MFA) for critical operations.
- Encryption in transit and at rest using TLS 1.3 and AES-256, ensuring confidentiality and integrity of operational and personal data.
- Granular access control through Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) and Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC), integrated with programmable policy enforcement to reduce human error.
- Comprehensive auditability, including secure logging, tamper-evident records, and traceability mechanisms aligned with IEC 62351-100.

- Privacy-by-design measures, enforcing data minimization, purpose limitation, and explicit user consent management for all personal or household-level data.

Interoperability with external infrastructures was addressed by defining integration scenarios with EW Digital Spine and Simpl Middleware. The definition of API requirements and supported data formats, exemplified through the EW Digital Spine Client, provides a concrete blueprint for implementing secure and standardised data exchange within U2Demo. By detailing both RESTful and WebSocket APIs, along with modules for authentication, credential management, client gateway configuration, topic and channel handling, and secure messaging, the deliverable ensures a clear pathway for integration with Simpl Middleware and other interoperability layers. The inclusion of well-defined data formats (JSON JSD-7 specification, CSV, TSV, XML) further supports consistency across pilots and external systems. These specifications should be directly leveraged in the next stages of platform and middleware development (T3.3, T3.4, T3.5) to maintain alignment between the semantic model, interoperability framework, and operational implementation.

Finally, the cybersecurity works also identified specific risks for P2P energy environments, such as rogue node injection, data manipulation, and unauthorized control signal execution, and proposed mitigations, including device attestation, anomaly detection, and secure onboarding protocols. The framework is designed to evolve alongside emerging threats and regulatory updates, and will be validated through deployment in the four pilot sites.

Overall, this deliverable ensures that U2Demo enters the platform development phase with a clear, standard-aligned semantic model and a robust, EU-compliant security and privacy framework, both of which are essential for achieving scalable, replicable, and trustworthy energy community solutions.

6.2 Implications for Standardization and Interoperability in U2Demo Platform Development

The findings highlight that U2Demo must operate as both a technical integrator and a standards catalyst.

Key implications include:

- **Semantic alignment is essential:** Without a common ontology, the heterogeneity in data models, formats, and protocols would severely hinder interoperability. The modular U2Demo ontology provides a scalable foundation for aligning partner systems and enabling automated data interpretation.
- **Bridging proprietary and open ecosystems:** Many pilots depend on vendor-specific APIs and closed platforms; therefore, U2Demo's architecture must include adapters, translators, or middleware to bridge these to standard-compliant interfaces.
- **Interoperability beyond the project:** By aligning with European interoperability frameworks (SAREF, SEAS, ENERSHARE) and integration initiatives like Simple, U2Demo enhances its potential for cross-border replication and participation in wider energy data spaces.
- **Security as a precondition for interoperability:** Interoperability specifications cannot be isolated from cybersecurity requirements. The security baseline defined in this deliverable, including authentication, encryption, access control, and auditing, must be applied to all standardized interfaces to ensure data and control signal trustworthiness.

6.3 Next Steps

The technical and methodological outputs of this deliverable form the foundation for the next stages of U2Demo platform development and pilot integration. The next steps are as follows:

1. Formal implementation of the ontology in OWL 2/RDF-Turtle, including persistent namespace publication, version management, and public repository hosting.
2. API specification and data modelling in the Deliverable D3.3, transforming the conceptual ontology modules into operational schemas and interface definitions. These specifications will include serializations for semantic payloads and mappings to pilot-specific datasets.
3. Integration testing with Simpl Middleware to validate end-to-end interoperability between pilot systems and the shared data exchange layer, including the secure handling of both operational and personal data.
4. Tasks T3.3 (*Development of P2P Energy Sharing Platform Using Blockchain Technologies*), T3.4 (*Internal and External Interfaces and Middleware*), and T3.5 (*APPs and Tools for users' interaction (Frontend)*) should be closely aligned with the recommendations and insights presented in this deliverable. This includes ensuring that platform development, middleware integration, and related technical components incorporate the defined interoperability requirements, semantic modelling approach, and security considerations, thereby maintaining consistency across design, implementation, and deployment activities.

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8 APPENDIX A: Questionnaire on Standards, Interoperability, and Cybersecurity

Questionnaire

Use of open-source P2P energy sharing platforms for energy democratization

This questionnaire aims to gather insights on the standards, interoperability, and cybersecurity requirements for the U2Demo P2P Energy Trading and Sharing platform. The responses will help define technical specifications, identify integration challenges, and ensure compliance with best practices.

Partner's information
Name:
E-mail:
Organisation:

Summary
Role in the U2Demo project

Standards and Interoperability: Interoperability is crucial for integrating diverse energy systems, ensuring seamless communication between different stakeholders, and maximizing the platform's usability. This section helps us understand the standards in use, identify potential gaps, and ensure compatibility with the U2Demo platform.

Question	Answer
1. What standards and/or protocols do you use (or plan to use) in your systems for data exchange? (e. g. OPENADR, SAREF, OCPI, CIM, BIM, BEM, IEC-61850, others).	e.g., we use OPENADR for demand response, IEC-61850 for grid communication, and OCPI for electric vehicle charging data ...

<p>Please specify the standards/protocols and the data being exchanged for each (see example).</p>	
<p>2. Does you (your organization) developed/implemented or foresee any extensions or adaptations of the standards or defining new ones for better interoperability in P2P energy sharing? If so, which ones and why?</p>	<p>e. g. yes, we propose extending SAREF to better support P2P energy transactions by adding metadata for local pricing mechanismsYes, we developed an extension for OCPI to support local energy tariffs.</p>
<p>3. How would you rate the adequacy of the existing standards for enabling P2P energy trading and energy sharing?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Very adequate <input type="checkbox"/> Adequate <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat inadequate <input type="checkbox"/> Very inadequate Why? e.g., while standards exist, they lack support for dynamic tariff updates</p>
<p>4. Have encountered (in previous projects) or do you expect to encounter (in this project) any specific limitations in current standards/protocols?</p>	<p>e.g., many standards are designed for centralized energy markets. There is a lack of standardized protocols for distributed energy trading ... Yes, IEC-61850 does not natively support peer-to-peer transactions, requiring workarounds.</p>
<p>5. What regulations impact the adoption standards regarding P2P energy sharing in your country? Please specify the standard and its constraints (see example).</p>	<p>e.g. yes, regulations in Germany require that P2P energy trading follows national grid tariffs, limiting our flexibility ... GDPR imposes constraints on personal data sharing, requiring anonymization in transactions.</p>
<p>6. Have you already implemented interfaces (e.g., APIs, communication protocols) to ensure interoperability between different systems/platforms? If yes, could you describe the process?</p>	<p>e.g. yes, we developed an API gateway for translating IEC-61850 messages into MQTT for IoT compatibility.... Yes, we use REST APIs for exchanging consumption data with third-party platforms.</p>
<p>7. What are the key interoperability challenges you anticipate in integrating your pilot with the U2Demo platform? What challenges have you faced regarding interoperability in previous projects?</p>	<p>e.g. data model misalignment between platforms, Latency issues for real-time transactions ... Different pilots use varying data formats, requiring conversion layers for compatibility</p>
<p>8. Have you used/implemented SIMPL Middleware or aligned developments with Gaia-X principles in previous projects? If yes, what are the main challenges/barriers and requirements you identified when integrating Gaia-X and SIMPL Middleware?</p>	<p>e.g. yes, we participated in an EU project on Gaia-X for energy data spaces but have not used Simpl Middleware yet ... Not yet, but we are assessing its feasibility for secure data sharing</p>
<p>9. How do you evaluate the readiness of your systems to exchange data using standardized interfaces and ontologies (semantic interoperability)?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Fully ready <input type="checkbox"/> Partially ready <input type="checkbox"/> Requires significant modifications <input type="checkbox"/> Not ready</p>
<p>10. Which data models or ontologies do you use to represent energy assets and data exchanges?</p>	<p>e.g. SAREF, CIM, and custom JSON-LD-based schemas for energy transactions ...</p>
<p>11. Are you familiar with Omega-X Common Semantic Data Model? And Smart Data Models?</p>	

12. What communication protocols do you use for energy asset data exchange (e.g., MQTT, REST API, WebSockets, OPC-UA, other)?	e.g. MQTT, REST API ... We use MQTT for real-time messaging and REST APIs for periodic updates.
13. Are there any proprietary solutions in your pilot that may pose a challenge for interoperability?	e. g. Yes, our local energy market algorithm is proprietary and does not natively support standard APIs. To enable interoperability, we may need to develop an API adapter that translates our internal data formats into standard protocols used by U2Demo ...
14. How do you currently handle data synchronization across different platforms and stakeholders?	e.g. using Kafka message queues and blockchain timestamps for transaction consistency... We use timestamped data with an event-driven architecture to ensure consistency.

Pilot Data interoperability (If you are not involved in a pilot you can jump to the next section): Interoperability relies on a clear understanding of the data each pilot solution requires, generates, and exchanges. These questions help identify supported data formats, collection methods, and protocols to ensure integration with the U2Demo platform. By addressing these aspects, we can anticipate compatibility challenges and design effective solutions for standardized data exchange.

15. In your pilot, what kind of data is required to be exchanged with the U2DEMO platform?	e.g. Smart meter readings, grid congestion status, and market prices.
16. What are the currently supported means for gathering this data?	e.g. Data is collected via IoT sensors, APIs from DSOs, and manual CSV uploads
17. What input data formats does your solution currently support? Do they adhere to a specific standard?	e.g. We support JSON, XML, and CSV... Yes, we use CIM-based JSON for energy transactions."
18. What kind of data does your solution provide?	e.g. Aggregated consumption reports and forecasted energy availability
19. What are the currently supported means for providing this data?	e.g. We expose a REST API and offer periodic data exports via SFTP
20. Do you require bidirectional data exchange, or will your systems mainly send or receive data to the U2Demo platform?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No, mainly send data <input type="checkbox"/> No, mainly receive data
21. Do you require real-time data exchange with the U2Demo platform?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Frequency required for your pilot:

Cybersecurity and Data Privacy: Ensuring a secure P2P trading environment is essential to prevent unauthorized access, fraud, and data breaches. This section helps us assess cybersecurity risks and identify necessary security measures.

22. What cybersecurity measures are currently in place in your systems? (Encryption, access management, data security, etc.)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Encryption (TLS, AES, etc.) <input type="checkbox"/> Secure authentication mechanisms (OAuth, PKI, etc.) <input type="checkbox"/> Role-based access control <input type="checkbox"/> Intrusion detection/prevention systems <input type="checkbox"/> Regular security audits <input type="checkbox"/> Other(s), please specify:
23. What encryption techniques are used for data at rest and in transit?	e.g. AES-256 for data at rest, TLS 1.3 for data in transit.
24. What are the main cybersecurity risks you perceive in a P2P energy	e.g. data integrity risks (e.g., fake transactions), Unauthorized access to trading algorithms, Man-

sharing platform? And data privacy related risks?	in-the-middle attacks on energy transactions ...ensuring GDPR compliance for energy transaction logs, preventing market manipulation through data leaks ...
25. What are the assets (software and/or hardware) you consider more critical in your demo regarding cybersecurity?	e. g. user transaction data, P2P pricing algorithms ...
26. What are the main cybersecurity threats you have identified in similar projects?	e.g. IoT device vulnerabilities (hacked smart meters), phishing attacks targeting market operators ...
27. What data protection and user privacy practices have you implemented in your systems?	e.g. Anonymization of trading data ...
28. How do you handle identity verification and user authentication in your systems?	e.g. Multi-factor authentication (MFA) and decentralized identifiers (DIDs) ...
29. How do you ensure compliance with GDPR or other data protection regulations in your country?	e.g. data minimization (only necessary user data is stored), DPIA, ...
30. Have you worked with confidential computing technologies before? (If yes, what tools and approaches have you used?)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, we are already using them <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, but not using them yet <input type="checkbox"/> No, but we are interested in exploring them <input type="checkbox"/> No, and we do not see a need If yes, tell us more about your experience:
31. How is data securely exchanged between energy producers, consumers, and grid operators?	e.g. Using end-to-end encryption and secure communication channels.
32. What protocols are used for secure communication?	e.g. TLS 1.3 for HTTP-based communication, IPSec for VPN connections.
33. Are smart contracts used for managing energy transactions? If so, have they been audited?	e.g. yes, we use Ethereum-based smart contracts, which were externally audited.
34. What authentication mechanisms are in place?	e.g. PKI-based authentication and OAuth2 for API access.
35. Is there a plan for incident response in case of a cybersecurity breach?	e.g. Yes, we have a predefined incident response playbook with escalation procedures.
36. What mechanisms are in place to ensure regulatory reporting and auditing?	e.g. Automated logging and audit trails compliant with GDPR and NIS2.
37. Are payment transactions secured using blockchain or the traditional financial system?	e.g. A mix – we use blockchain for settlement but traditional banks for fiat transactions.
38. Is there a dispute resolution mechanism for incorrect or malicious energy transactions?	e.g. Yes, a multi-step arbitration process involving smart contract validation.
39. Do you have security measures against rogue nodes injecting false data into the system?	e.g. Yes, we implement anomaly detection algorithms to flag suspicious data
40. Do you foresee any challenges in implementing confidential computing in your system?	e.g. integration complexity with existing cloud infrastructure ...

Other Observations and Suggestions	
41. Do you have any additional suggestions or concerns regarding standards, cybersecurity, or the integration of the U2Demo platform?	

9 APPENDIX B: Questionnaire Answers and complete analysis

9.1 Questionnaire Responses Analysis

This section provides a detailed analysis of the questionnaire responses, following a structured, question-by-question approach. For each item, the analysis outlines key observations, examines their implications for the interoperability of the U2Demo platform, and considers the relevance and application of existing standards and protocols. In addition to interpreting the responses, the analysis identifies potential technical and regulatory challenges, and offers recommendations and conclusions that can inform the platform’s design and integration strategy. This in-depth assessment supports the broader objectives of Task T3.2 by translating partner input into actionable insights for the development of a robust, standard-compliant, and secure P2P energy sharing infrastructure.

Analysis of Question 1: What standards and/or protocols do you use (or plan to use) in your systems for data exchange? (e. g. OPENADR, SAREF, OCPI, CIM, BIM, BEM, IEC-61850, others). Please specify the standards/protocols and the data being exchanged for each (see example).

- **Current Use of Standards/Protocols:**

Partner	Protocols/Standards in Use	Data Exchanged
EnGreen	Vendor-specific Huawei protocols (via FusionSolar App)	PV production, battery status, energy flows (self-consumption, grid exchange, intra-EC sharing)
DHAAG	MODBus, MQTT, HTTP APIs, WebSocket (via OpenRemote)	Production/consumption, battery SoC, grid interaction, load/battery control signals
KLIMAAN	Huawei API (vendor-specific), EnergieID, Fluvius CSV	PV production and consumption data (collected via EnergieID), CSV/SFTP data from grid operator
NEW	RESTful APIs, SAREF	P2P exchange data, billing, settlement logs, semantic interoperability data
INESC	Modbus, VE-Direct, (planned: OpenADR, OCPP)	PV inverter data, potentially EV charging and P2P trading protocols
Watt-IS	OpenADR (used), SAREF (used in a past project)	Flexibility events (OpenADR); semantic data exchange for DSO services (SAREF)

- **Planned Adoption of Standards:**

Partner	Standards/Protocols Planned	Intended Data Use
EnGreen	Open to standard adoption	Broad EC member energy data (PV, battery, consumption, etc.)

KLIMAAN	OCPI (for charging infrastructure)	EV charging infrastructure communication
INESC	OCPP, OpenADR, P2P trading protocol	EV charging, flexibility test, energy trading

- **Conclusions:**

Most partners are currently using a mix of standard and proprietary protocols, with a clear interest in expanding toward open, interoperable frameworks. Protocols like OpenADR, SAREF, Modbus, and REST APIs are gaining traction due to their flexibility, compatibility with energy management systems, and role in smart grid services.

The responses suggest a progressive but fragmented landscape, where common reference models (e.g., SAREF) and standardization efforts (e.g., OCPI, OCPP) can play a critical role in ensuring future interoperability and scalability across the U2Demo ecosystem.

Analysis of Question 2: Does you (your organization) developed/implemented or foresee any extensions or adaptations of the standards or defining new ones for better interoperability in P2P energy sharing? If so, which ones and why?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Intention to Develop or Extend Standards?	Details / Rationale
EnGreen	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (adopt/customize existing) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No new	Will adopt and adapt standards but not develop new ones; focus is on implementation, not standard creation.
DHAAG	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	Involved in extending <i>Firmware Smart Energy</i> and <i>CBRN standards</i> through EU projects <i>Reschool</i> and <i>Beholder</i> .
KLIMAAN	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	No extensions or adaptations foreseen.
NEW	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	No extensions or developments planned.
INESC	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	No extensions foreseen; reference made to unmet needs in P2P.
Watt-IS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (extension likely needed)	SAREF lacks specific support for REC and P2P energy sharing; sees need to extend it. Notes OpenADR not suitable for P2P.

- **Analysis:**

- The majority do not plan standard development: Four out of six partners (EnGreen, KLIMAAN, NEW, INESC) indicate no intention to define new standards. Their strategy leans toward adoption of existing standards or implementation of external solutions.
- Adaptation vs. Innovation:

- EnGreen plans to adapt existing standards but avoids creating new ones.
- Watt-IS identifies gaps in current standards (e.g. SAREF's limitations for P2P and REC contexts) and foresees a need to extend existing ontologies.
- Examples of Standard Evolution: DHAAG is actively contributing to standard extensions (Firmware Smart Energy, CBRN) via EU-funded projects — a relevant model of how community-driven standard evolution can happen.
- in P2P-Focused Interoperability Standards: Watt-IS and INESC raise concerns about the current standards' inadequacy for P2P energy sharing, reinforcing the need for tailored semantic models or enhancements (e.g. in SAREF or new APIs).
- **Conclusions:**

Although most organizations are not developing new standards, there is a clear recognition of current limitations, especially for P2P energy sharing scenarios. Some (like DHAAG and Watt-IS) are already exploring or recommending targeted extensions to existing standards. This highlights a strategic opportunity for collaborative efforts within U2Demo and the broader community to shape and contribute to interoperable frameworks adapted for energy communities and peer-based exchange models.

Analysis of Question 3: How would you rate the adequacy of the existing standards for enabling P2P energy trading and energy sharing?

- **Analysis:**
 - General scepticism about adequacy:
 - 4 of 6 partners express inadequacy to some degree (3 label the current standards as “somewhat inadequate” and 1 (KLIMAAN) finds them “very inadequate”).
 - This suggests widespread recognition of functional gaps in standards, especially for P2P-specific use cases.
 - Concerns about what is missing:
 - High-level interoperability and semantic consistency are lacking (DHAAG, Watt-IS).
 - There is an absence of support for distributed micro-generation aggregation (EnGreen).
 - Trust and adoption of emerging frameworks like Fiware Smart Energy remains limited (DHAAG).
 - Contextual Adequacy:
 - INESC emphasizes that adequacy is architecture-dependent, particularly on the model of governance used in the P2P setting.

- NEW is an outlier, expressing that standards are adequate without concern, possibly due to more internal control or readiness to adapt.

- **Conclusions:**

There is a consensus across most partners that current standards only partially support the needs of P2P energy trading and sharing, especially when it comes to: Aggregating dispersed energy production; Semantic interoperability; Suitability for decentralized and dynamic exchange environments.

This highlights an opportunity for U2Demo and similar initiatives to propose or support enhancements to frameworks like SAREF and Fiware, and to bridge the gap between low-level communication protocols and higher-level interoperable energy services.

Analysis of Question 4: Have encountered (in previous projects) or do you expect to encounter (in this project) any specific limitations in current standards/protocols?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Limitations Reported	Details or Clarifications
EnGreen	No (not applicable)	Not the technology developer, so no direct experience with limitations.
NEW	No	No limitations experienced or anticipated.
INESC	No (so far)	No limitations up to this point.
Watt-IS	Yes	Anticipates modelling misalignments in U2Demo; past issues with proprietary data formats, especially handling errors.

- **Conclusions:**

While no widespread limitations have yet been experienced or identified, the feedback indicates that such issues may emerge during implementation, particularly around:

- Interoperability of proprietary formats;
- Semantic modelling mismatches;
- Handling non-standard or error data cases.

Watt-Is experience suggests that standardization gaps are subtle but impactful, often appearing in advanced phases of system integration. Therefore, ongoing monitoring and early semantic alignment may be critical during the project's next steps.

Analysis of Question 5: What regulations impact the adoption standards regarding P2P energy sharing in your country? Please specify the standard and its constraints.

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Country	Regulatory Impact on P2P Energy Sharing	Constraints Identified
EnGreen	Italy	National regulations impose grid code and metering compliance via ARERA	Limits flexibility in local energy exchanges
DHAAG	Netherlands	Electricity Act restricts delivery to licensed suppliers	P2P allowed only in closed systems (e.g. buildings)
KLIMAAN	Belgium	No answer provided	–
NEW	Portugal	Only certified energy suppliers can trade electricity	Blocks residential P2P energy trading
INESC	Portugal	No specific regulation identified	–
Watt-IS	Portugal	Regulation not supportive of P2P sharing; GDPR requirements for data sharing	Consent from all participants needed even in simulations

- **Conclusions:**

Regulatory frameworks across the participating countries currently present significant obstacles to full-scale P2P energy trading, especially in open, market-driven environments. These obstacles range from licensing restrictions to stringent data protection requirements.

This suggests that:

- Pilot and demonstration activities will be conducted in real operational environments whenever possible, with simulation-based or closed-system implementations considered only when technical, regulatory, or operational constraints make alternative approaches unfeasible.
- Efforts to align technical developments (like interoperability standards) must also account for ongoing regulatory evolution.
- The success of standards adoption is not solely a technical issue but is tightly interwoven with national legal frameworks and data governance policies.

Analysis of Question 6: Have you already implemented interfaces (e.g., APIs, communication protocols) to ensure interoperability between different systems/platforms? If yes, could you describe the process?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Implemented Interfaces?	Approach / Description
EnGreen	✗ No	Intends to implement APIs or protocols in U2Demo, especially for accessing data from proprietary inverter platforms.
DHAAG	✓ Yes	REST APIs used for exchanging data with external platforms; developing an API for day-ahead forecasting and a GOPACS interface for congestion management.

KLIMAAN	✗ No	No implementation reported.
NEW	✓ Yes	Multiple data acquisition methods: DSO platform access, REC manager rights, and APIs from installed sensors. Also uses APIs between applications (Docker-based architecture).

- **Key Observations:**

- Partially Established Interoperability:
 - DHAAG and NEW have already implemented specific interfaces for system integration and data exchange.
 - DHAAG shows the most mature setup, integrating both real-time operations and forecasting, and even aligning with national congestion platforms like GOPACS.
- Custom / Non-standard Interfaces: The solutions reported are largely customized (tailor-made) rather than based on widely adopted interoperability standards, reinforcing the gap in practical implementations of existing protocols.
- No Current Implementation but Planned: EnGreen is focused on implementing such capabilities as a key deliverable of the U2Demo project, especially for bridging access to data from proprietary inverter ecosystems.
- Indirect Access Paths: NEW uses a mix of institutional access rights and hardware-based sensing to collect data and shares information via APIs internally between microservices (e.g., Dockers), showing a hybrid and pragmatic approach.

- **Conclusions:**

The answers indicate a diverse level of maturity in interoperability implementation across partners. While some, like DHAAG and NEW, are already leveraging APIs and communication protocols, others are in planning or aspiration stages. The current trend leans towards custom-built integrations, underscoring a need for more standardized and modular interoperability frameworks, a key challenge U2Demo aims to address.

Analysis of Question 7: What are the key interoperability challenges you anticipate in integrating your pilot with the U2Demo platform? What challenges have you faced regarding interoperability in previous projects?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Anticipated / Previous Interoperability Challenges
EnGreen	Installation of smart devices needed for interoperability is pending. Challenges expected in procurement and deployment (planned for 2025).
DHAAG	Standard interoperability protocols are often too generic and heavy, requiring significant development effort compared to custom solutions.

KLIMAAN	Difficulty in structuring and retrieving data as needed—need for a platform to organize and access data efficiently.
NEW	Challenges in accessing real-time data due to different data owners. Coordination and permissions create barriers to effective data integration.
INESC	Electric mobility interoperability is generally problematic, but this is not relevant to U2Demo’s planned implementation.

- **Key Observations:**

- **Technical Readiness & Infrastructure Barriers:** EnGreen highlights the infrastructure side of interoperability as a challenge, delays in installing the necessary hardware could hinder data exchange and integration.
- **Complexity of Standard Adoption:** DHAAG provides a critical insight: while standardization is a long-term goal, overly broad or general standards introduce development overhead and may not align well with lean or focused pilot needs.
- **Data Structuring and Accessibility:** KLIMAAN and NEW raise concerns about the practicalities of data access, including organizing data and navigating ownership or permission issues, a common issue in multi-stakeholder environments.
- **Domain-Specific Gaps:** IINESC flags electric mobility as an area with known interoperability issues but notes it will not impact the U2Demo pilot directly.

- **Conclusions:**

The responses to this question underscore that interoperability challenges are multifaceted, ranging from technical constraints (hardware, real-time access) to organizational and regulatory barriers (data ownership, standard maturity). There is a notable trade-off between using well-established standards and developing lean, purpose-built integrations. For U2Demo, anticipating these constraints early and fostering modular, adaptable solutions will be critical to smooth platform integration across diverse pilot contexts.

Analysis of Question 8: Have you used/implemented SIMPL Middleware or aligned developments with Gaia-X principles in previous projects? If yes, what are the main challenges/barriers and requirements you identified when integrating Gaia-X and SIMPL Middleware?

All partners reported NO usage/implementation of SIMPL Middleware or aligned developments with Gaia-X principles in previous projects.

Analysis of Question 9: How do you evaluate the readiness of your systems to exchange data using standardized interfaces and ontologies (semantic interoperability)?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Readiness of partner systems
EnGreen	Not Ready
DHAAG	Requires significant modifications

KLIMAAN	Not Ready
NEW	Partially Ready
INESC	Partially Ready
Watt-IS	Partially Ready

- **Key Observations:**

- Low Overall Readiness: None of the six partners declared their systems as “fully ready.” This reflects a general lack of maturity in semantic interoperability across the pilot implementations.
- "Not Ready" Group: EnGreen and KLIMAAN explicitly state they are not ready to use standardized interfaces and ontologies. This suggests these partners may require both technical support and system upgrades to align with the U2Demo interoperability objectives.
- "Requires Modifications": DHAAG acknowledges the need for significant modifications, indicating some foundational capabilities are present, but major development work is still needed.
- "Partially Ready" Group: NEW, INESC, and Watt-Is rate their readiness as partial, these partners are in a better position to engage in semantic interoperability efforts but will likely require targeted adaptations or integration work.

- **Conclusions:**

The assessment indicates that semantic interoperability readiness is a key challenge area for U2Demo. While some partners have initial capabilities or partial integration experience, a substantial effort will be required, especially for partners starting from scratch or needing to overhaul existing setups. The project may benefit from offering common tools, integration templates, or shared support services to reduce the burden and harmonize semantic data exchange across all pilots.

Analysis of Question 10: Which data models or ontologies do you use to represent energy assets and data exchanges?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Data Models / Ontologies Used
EnGreen	In-house (Excel, Python models) for energy production, consumption, and exchanges
DHAAG	Fiware Smart Energy data models
KLIMAN	Not specified
NEW	Smart Data Models (FIWARE, TM Forum, IUDX, OASC, etc.) and SAREF
INESC	JSON
Watt-IS	JSON-LD based approach (used in another project for NILM – Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring – service)

- **Key Observations:**

- Diversity in Maturity and Adoption:

- A broad range of data modelling strategies is observed—from basic in-house tools (Excel, Python) to standardized ontologies (SAREF, JSON-LD, Smart Data Models).
- This reflects a non-uniform maturity level across partners in terms of structured, interoperable data representation.

- Standardized and Open Data Models:

- NEW demonstrates advanced alignment with Smart Data Models and SAREF, showing a strong orientation toward interoperable and scalable solutions.
- Watt-Is uses a semantic JSON-LD approach for lightweight, web-friendly semantic interoperability.

- Pragmatic and Tailored Approaches:

- EnGreen relies on custom-built tools for internal use, which might lack interoperability unless transitioned to standard models.
- INESC and DHAAG employ structured but varying models, JSON and FIWARE respectively, suggesting some readiness for structured data, though not all are semantically enriched.

- Gaps in Reporting: Kliman did not provide an answer, which might signal limited adoption or low familiarity with data model standards.

- **Conclusions:**

The responses show that while some partners (e.g., NEW, Watt-Is) are engaging with standardized, semantically rich data models, others are still working with custom or informal solutions, potentially hindering cross-platform interoperability. As a next step, it would be beneficial for the project to:

- Promote adoption of common data models, such as SEAS, SAREF and others.
- Provide conversion templates or mapping support from in-house structures to standard ontologies.
- Ensure documentation and support are available for teams unfamiliar with semantic modelling.

Analysis of Question 11: Are you familiar with Omega-X Common Semantic Data Model (CSDM)? And Smart Data Models?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Familiarity with Omega-X / Smart Data Models
EnGreen	Somewhat familiar with <i>Smart Data Models</i> (in the context of smart meter data); no mention of Omega-X.
DHAAG	Not familiar with either.
KLIMAAN	Not familiar with either.
EDP New	Some familiarity (no details provided).
INESC	Not familiar with either.
Watt-IS	Not familiar with Omega-X. Has experience with <i>SAREF ontologies</i> through another European project (InterConnect).

- **Key Observations:**

1. Limited Awareness of Omega-X CSDM:

- None of the partners explicitly confirm familiarity with the Omega-X Common Semantic Data Model (CSDM).
- Watt-IS explicitly states unfamiliarity.
- This indicates a low awareness or usage of Omega-X CSDM across the consortium.

2. Partial Exposure to Smart Data Models:

- EnGreen and NEW have some familiarity with Smart Data Models, but mostly tied to practical implementations (e.g., smart meters) rather than semantic modelling frameworks.
- Watt-IS shows higher conceptual exposure through its work with SAREF and the InterConnect project, but not Smart Data Models specifically.

3. Capacity Building Opportunity: With at least 4 out of 6 partners either unfamiliar or only loosely aware of these models, the project may benefit from training, demos, or guided onboarding into semantic interoperability frameworks.

- **Conclusions:**

Most partners have had little direct interaction with Omega-X CSDM and Smart Data Models, as these frameworks have only recently emerged in the energy data domain. While current familiarity is limited, these models may offer useful reference points for future semantic alignment, alongside other options under consideration as the U2Demo platform evolves.

Analysis of Question 12: What communication protocols do you use for energy asset data exchange (e.g., MQTT, REST API, WebSockets, OPC-UA, other)?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Protocols Used
EnGreen	None currently; plans to implement in U2Demo pilot.
DHAAG	MODBus, MQTT, REST API; possibly BACnet and OCPI in future.

KLIMAAN	REST API, WebSocket (via EnergyID), SFTP (CSV files).
NEW	REST API and SFTP (as per setup described in Question 6).
INESC	MQTT, REST API, WebSocket, WebHook.
Watt-IS	SFTP (for smart metering data from DSO), REST API for integration with energy asset data.

- **Key Observations and Protocol Usage Trends:**

- REST API is the most commonly mentioned protocol: Used or planned by 5 out of 6 partners (DHAAG, KLIMAAN, NEW, INESC, Watt-IS).
- SFTP is also widely used: Especially for structured data exchange (NEW, KLIMAAN, Watt-IS).
- MQTT and WebSocket: Adopted or considered by DHAAG, INESC, KLIMAAN (via EnergyID).
- Others: MODBus (DHAAG) and WebHook (INESC) show further diversity. BACnet and OCPI mentioned as planned by DHAAG.
- REST APIs and SFTP dominate current implementations, suggesting a mix of modern integration practices with more traditional file-based methods for DSO-related exchanges.
- Protocol diversity is present, especially from partners like INESC and DHAAG who use multiple protocols to accommodate various device ecosystems.
- No standardized common approach yet across partners — this could pose integration challenges unless unified interface specifications are defined under U2Demo.

- **Conclusions:**

The partners use a heterogeneous mix of communication protocols for energy asset data exchange, with REST APIs and SFTP standing out as common denominators. However, the variation in other protocols (MQTT, MODBus, WebSocket, etc.) highlights a need for interoperability coordination within the project to streamline data integration and ensure robust cross-platform communication. This diversity also presents an opportunity to define interface guidelines or introduce middleware within U2Demo to bridge protocol differences.

Analysis of Question 13: Are there any proprietary solutions in your pilot that may pose a challenge for interoperability?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Proprietary Solutions	Interoperability Challenge
EnGreen	Proprietary inverter apps (e.g., FusionSolar, etc.) for individual prosumer data	Data is private; requires privacy policy approval; lack of API or standard interface

DHAAG	None internally (OpenRemote is fully open source)	Relies on open contributions and adherence to API and documentation standards
KLIMAAN	Huawei API; EnergyID	Vendor-specific APIs; may need integration layers
NEW	DSO data in predefined proprietary format (sgl_v2); bi-directional comm via sFTP	Requires automation, data translation to U2Demo format, and additional API setup
INESC	Modbus and VE-Direct protocols	Require mapping into standard interfaces for full semantic interoperability
Watt-IS	Proprietary flexibility management and other services	Uses OpenAPI specs to expose service interfaces; not standardized outside OpenADR

- **Key Observations and Protocol Usage Trends:**

- Most pilots rely on at least one proprietary component, especially at the device level (e.g., inverter APIs, DSO data feeds).
- Vendor lock-in (Huawei, proprietary formats) and closed APIs are common and require translators or adapters for integration.
- Open-source strategies (like OpenRemote) mitigate challenges but still depend on active community development and standard adherence.
- Semantic mapping and standard model alignment (as required by U2Demo) remains a consistent technical need.
- Implications for U2Demo:
 - Custom integration layers or middleware will likely be required to align all data flows with the common semantic model.
 - Data privacy and ownership concerns (EnGreen, DSO data) will necessitate not just technical, but legal and organizational frameworks.
 - Standardized APIs or wrappers (e.g., OpenAPI for Watt-Is) can be used to bridge proprietary systems, but may not fully cover semantics or interoperability constraints.

- **Conclusions:**

Proprietary solutions are present in nearly all pilots, often creating significant challenges for data access, semantic translation, and system compatibility. Addressing these will be essential for seamless integration into U2Demo, requiring both technical tools (APIs, translators) and project wide agreements on data governance, privacy, and standard mappings.

Analysis of Question 14: How do you currently handle data synchronization across different platforms and stakeholders?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Synchronization Method	Remarks / Observations
EnGreen	No current aggregation; possible future synchronization through inverter apps (proprietary, per prosumer)	Privacy concerns; synchronization not yet implemented
DHAAG	Dedicated API exchanges; uses open-source Balena for firmware synchronization on edge devices	API-based tailored integration; firmware handled separately
KLIMAAN	Manual synchronization	Not scalable; likely to cause delays or inconsistencies
NEW	No synchronization strategy in place	Indicates need for planning synchronization mechanisms
INESC	Uses timestamps to align and synchronize data flows	Lightweight but effective approach for time-based data coordination

- **Key Observations and Protocol Usage Trends:**

- Lack of structured synchronization is a common issue:
 - 3 out of 6 partners have no synchronization or only manual processes in place.
 - This may pose risks for data consistency, particularly in real-time or near-real-time energy trading scenarios.
- Use of timestamps (INESC) is a promising lightweight method for ensuring temporal alignment of distributed data sources.
- API-based synchronization (DHAAG) demonstrates a more mature approach, which could be a reference for others, especially for edge device coordination.
- Privacy and platform fragmentation (as noted by Engreen) limit shared data visibility and may hinder seamless integration unless resolved.

Implications for U2Demo:

Unified synchronization framework may be required across pilots, possibly through:

- i. Standard API gateways;
- ii. Common timestamp and metadata schemes;
- iii. Shared data lakes or brokers with synchronization logic.

- **Conclusions:**

Current synchronization practices across the pilots are heterogeneous and mostly underdeveloped, with only a few examples of automated or scalable solutions.

The following set of questions refer to Pilot Data interoperability. Interoperability relies on a clear understanding of the data each pilot solution requires, generates, and exchanges. These answers to these questions will help the identification of supported data formats, collection methods, and protocols to ensure integration with the U2Demo platform.

Analysis of Question 15: In you pilot, what kind of data is required to be exchanged with the U2DEMO platform?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Types of Data Required for Exchange	Notes / Specifics
EnGreen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local energy production - Energy consumption - Energy storage - Shared energy (6-monthly from GSE) - Market prices - Environmental & monitoring data 	Shared energy data not real-time; calculated or obtained from national authority
KLIMAAN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart meter readings (monthly) - Inverter data (5-min interval) - Market prices (future) - Possible grid congestion status (live) 	Focus on solar PV data and potential inclusion of grid data
NEW	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Household consumption and production 	Simple and to the point
INESC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meter data (Shelly devices) - Inverter data - Scheduling & forecasting - Energy prices - (Possibly) service activation 	Rich data set including forecasts and service coordination
Watt-IS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart meter readings (primarily) <i>(Due to lack of P2P regulation in Portugal)</i> 	Contextual limitation due to regulatory environment

- **Key Observations:**

- Common Data Types Across Pilots:

- Smart meter data, inverter data, and market prices are shared across nearly all partners.
- These represent the core data streams needed for P2P monitoring and optimization.

- Real-Time vs. Periodic:

- Some pilots (e.g., KLIMAAN) note 5-minute resolution for inverter data, others only have monthly availability.
- Temporal granularity may pose interoperability challenges for unified platform services.

- Country-Specific Constraints: Watt-IS and EnGreen highlight regulatory barriers (Portugal, Italy) limiting what kind of data (and at what frequency) can be exchanged.
- Advanced Data Needs: INESC is preparing forecasting, scheduling, and service activation data – indicating greater system maturity and integration ambitions.
- **Recommendations for U2Demo Platform Design:**
 - Minimum data set should include:
 - Smart meter consumption and production
 - Inverter operational data
 - Price signals (market-based or simulated)
 - Metadata schemas should account for:
 - Sampling rate (e.g., 5 min, monthly)
 - Data origin (manual input, sensor, third-party platform)
 - Privacy & consent layers should be designed for:
 - Proprietary platforms (e.g., inverter apps)
 - Government-provided data (e.g., GSE in Italy)
- **Conclusions:**

While all partners converge around energy production/consumption and market data, significant diversity exists in granularity, source accessibility, and regulatory constraints. U2Demo must prepare for heterogeneous data ingestion and provide mapping/normalization capabilities to ensure successful platform integration across pilots.

Analysis of Question 16: What are the currently supported means for gathering this data?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Data Collection Methods	Sources
EnGreen	- Smart meters linked to inverter monitoring apps (e.g., FusionSolar) - Internet connection required - No smart meters for consumers yet	Inverter apps (producers only)
DHAAG	- REST APIs via OpenRemote - MQTT or HTTP agents for sending setpoints	OpenRemote, device APIs
KLIMAAN	- DSO API (being phased out due to consent issues) - CSV uploads via SFTP from DSO - Inverter API (Huawei/Solar Fusion)	DSO platform, inverter APIs

NEW	- Access via DSO platform (“Balcão Digital da E-REDES”) through sFTP (in development) -Monthly access to all data as REC manager -API to Shelly smart devices installed in households	DSO, Shelly devices, REC role
INESC	- To be discussed	TBD
Watt-IS	- WIS-Connector: proprietary IoT device connecting to DSO smart meter HAN port - Ingestion of SGL files via SFTP - User metadata via platform	Smart meter (HAN), user platform input, SFTP

- **Key Observations:**

- Common Collection Modes:

- Smart meters (DSO or local) and inverter APIs are widely used where available.
- SFTP and REST APIs are dominant transfer mechanisms.

- Data Source Diversity:

- Some partners (like KLIMAAN, Watt-IS) rely on external utility sources (DSOs).
- Others (like NEW and DHAAG) integrate direct hardware and API connections (e.g., Shelly devices, OpenRemote).

- Technology Readiness:

- NEW and Watt-IS show higher maturity with multi-source acquisition pipelines and automation.
- EnGreen still faces foundational limitations (e.g., no consumption smart meters yet).

- Proprietary vs Open Source: Watt-IS and DHAAG mention use of proprietary tools (e.g., WIS-Connector) and open platforms (e.g., OpenRemote), balancing flexibility and integration effort.

- **Challenges identified:**

- Data Ownership & Consent: KLIMAAN reports difficulties obtaining permission to use DSO APIs.

- Hardware Limitations: EnGreen lacks consumer-side smart meters, hindering full data visibility.

- Technical Integration: Disparities in real-time capability (e.g., monthly vs live data) can impact synchronization and analysis.

- **Recommendations for U2Demo Platform:**

- Support diverse ingestion formats: APIs, SFTP, CSV, and user-input interfaces.

- Abstract data input layers: Use adapters or connectors to normalize proprietary and varied protocols.
- Build trust & simplify consent: Provide templates or support mechanisms for regulatory-compliant data access agreements.

- **Conclusions:**

This analysis confirms that while data collection methods are largely in place, integration uniformity and completeness will require targeted support within the U2Demo architecture.

Analysis of Question 17: What input data formats does your solution currently support? Do they adhere to a specific standard?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Input Data Formats	Standards Adhered To
EnGreen	Not clearly known; data managed via proprietary inverter app (Huawei FusionSolar)	Proprietary, not specified
DHAAG	OpenRemote supports HTTP, TCP, UDP, WebSockets, MQTT, etc.	Generic protocol support (no strict standard)
KLIMAAN	Via EnergyID: supports manual input, CSV, API	Proprietary, energy management focused
NEW	Excel and CSV datasets	Informal format, not standardised
INESC	Formats need adaptation to become standard-compliant	Not yet standardized
Watt-IS	SGL v2 via SFTP (DSO standard in Portugal), JSON via web platform or WIS-Connector	Partially standard (SGL v2), JSON-based formats

- **Key Observations:**

- Low Adherence to Common Standards:
 - Most partners do not yet follow standardised data formats for inputs.
 - Watt-IS is the only one explicitly using a known national standard (SGL v2).
- Diverse Input Channels:
 - Some use user interfaces (Watt-IS, KLIMAAN), others rely on data files (CSV/Excel) or API-supported data streams (DHAAG).
 - Format flexibility is present but standardisation remains an open issue.
- Interoperability Challenge: These varied formats will pose integration difficulties unless harmonized or mapped to a common semantic data model

- **Recommendations for U2Demo Platform:**

- Establish a common input schema: Define or adopt standard data models early and promote usage.
- Provide converters or wrappers: To handle partner-specific formats and harmonise them on ingestion.
- Standard alignment training: Encourage and support partners in aligning data formats to project wide ontology frameworks.

- **Conclusions:**

This analysis highlights that while data acquisition is operational across partners, input format heterogeneity may become a bottleneck for semantic and technical interoperability unless actively addressed.

Analysis of Question 18: What kind of data does your solution provide?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Type of Data Provided
EnGreen	Detailed operational data: production, grid interaction, consumption, environment (e.g. irradiance), inverter and battery status.
DHAAG	Extensive real-time and operational data: user-level power, PV/battery data, grid metrics, protection system status, etc.
KLIMAAN	Aggregated consumption reports.
NEW	Household-level consumption and production data.
INESC	Forecasting and scheduling data.
Watt-IS	Energy sharing quantification and related financial flow data among participants.

- **Key Observations:**

- Data Richness Varies Significantly:
 - EnGreen and DHAAG provide comprehensive and granular datasets across several operational domains (generation, grid metrics, device-level telemetry).
 - Others (like NEW and KLIMAAN) offer more aggregated or focused data sets.
- Financial & Transactional Layer (Watt-Is): Watt-Is uniquely provides quantitative and financial-level data on energy sharing — key for enabling market mechanisms and accounting in P2P trading.
- Planning and Forecasting Dimension (INESC): INESC brings forecasting/scheduling data, essential for optimization and coordination in decentralized energy systems.

- **Implications for U2Demo Interoperability:**

- The heterogeneity in data scope and granularity implies that the U2Demo platform must:
 - Accommodate both real-time telemetry and aggregated reports;
 - Support financial data flows and forecasting models;
 - Implement a flexible data ingestion architecture aligned with a common semantic framework to ensure consistency.

- **Recommendations for U2Demo Platform:**

- Ensure support for both technical KPIs and economic indicators to reflect the full lifecycle of P2P energy exchange.

- **Conclusions:**

This analysis underscores that while partners provide complementary types of data, the standardization and integration strategy must reflect this diversity to fully leverage their contributions.

Analysis of Question 19: What are the currently supported means for providing this data?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Means for Providing Data
EnGreen	CSV exports via smart meters and inverter app.
DHAAG	MQTT and REST API via OpenRemote.
KLIMAAN	Not specified.
NEW	sFTP access to DSO platform, direct access via API from smart devices (Shelly), monthly data from REC management.
INESC	MQTT, REST API, WebSocket, WebHook.
Watt-IS	Through a User Interface (UI).

- **Key Observations:**

- Variety of Delivery Mechanisms: Partners support a broad spectrum of data delivery methods — from modern web protocols (REST API, MQTT, WebSockets) to traditional file-based approaches (CSV, sFTP).
- API Adoption: DHAAG, INESC, and NEW all incorporate REST APIs, suggesting that API-based integration can be a key focus area for U2Demo.
- CSV and Manual Interfaces: EnGreen and Watt-IS rely on more manual or end-user oriented methods (CSV exports, UI tools), indicating the need for automation pipelines or middleware adapters for smooth integration.

- Data Intermediaries: NEW's layered access (DSO → REC → Devices) reflects multi-level data flow
- **Implications and Recommendations for U2Demo Platform:**
 - The U2Demo platform must:
 - Support multi-format ingestion (API, CSV, sFTP).
 - Handle asynchronous and batch data updates (e.g., monthly REC data).
 - Possibly provide data pre-processing or mapping tools for UI/manual inputs (e.g., from Watt-IS or EnGreen).
 - Design a pluggable data acquisition layer supporting:
 - File uploads (CSV/SGL)
 - Real-time streaming (MQTT/WebSockets)
 - RESTful pull/push models
 - Data validation/adaptation interfaces might be interesting to harmonize various data origins and ensure semantic consistency.
- **Conclusions:**

This question highlights the technical heterogeneity in how data is currently made available and suggests the need for an interoperable, adaptable integration framework within U2Demo.

Analysis of Question 20: Do you require bidirectional data exchange, or will your systems mainly send or receive data to the U2Demo platform?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Bidirectional Data Exchange Required?
EnGreen	Yes
DHAAG	Depends on the use case (To Be Defined)
KLIMAAN	Yes
NEW	Yes
INESC	Yes
Watt-IS	Yes

- **Key Observations:**
 - Strong Demand for Bidirectional Exchange: Most partners (5 out of 6) explicitly confirm the need for bidirectional communication, showing that U2Demo should not be designed as a one-way data collector.

- Functional Implications: Bidirectional exchange implies support for: i) Data retrieval and push (e.g., metering and forecasts); ii) Command or signal reception (e.g., setpoints, scheduling, flexibility dispatch).
- **Implications and Recommendations for U2Demo Platform:**
 - U2Demo must support:
 - Two-way communication protocols (e.g., RESTful APIs, MQTT, WebSocket).
 - Feedback mechanisms for partners to act upon U2Demo outputs.
 - Secure and auditable transaction handling to ensure trust in sent/received data.
 - Establish clear data exchange contracts with each pilot.
 - Prioritize development of modular APIs that support both data input (e.g., sensor readings) and output (e.g., optimization setpoints).
 - Ensure robust authentication and authorization mechanisms for both sending and receiving actors.
- **Conclusions:**

The responses underscore that U2Demo Platform is expected to be an active participant in data flows, emphasizing the importance of real-time and reciprocal data services in the platform design.

Analysis of Question 21: Do you require real-time data exchange with the U2Demo platform?

- **Answers summary table:**

Partner	Requires Real-Time Data Exchange?	Notes / Conditions
EnGreen	Yes	
DHAAG	To be defined	To be defined depending on use case
KLIMAAN	Yes	Especially relevant if neighborhood battery or EV charging is integrated
NEW	To be defined	Depends on U2Demo functionalities
INESC	Yes	
Watt-IS	No	

- **Key Observations:**
 - Majority of respondents see need for real-time exchange:
 - 3 out of 6 partners clearly affirm real-time needs.

- 2 partners (DHAAG and NEW) leave it conditional, depending on pilot scope or U2Demo capabilities.
- Only 1 partner (Watt-Is) explicitly does not require real-time interaction.
- Use-Case Dependency:
 - Real-time exchange is often tied to operational control, like storage, charging, or market signals.
 - Simpler data monitoring or retrospective reporting (e.g., by Watt-IS) can operate without real-time constraints.
- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**
 - Real-Time Capability: U2Demo should be architected for low-latency, high-availability data exchange, particularly for assets like batteries or dynamic pricing.
 - Scalability and Modularity: Real-time features could be made optional or modular to accommodate both high-speed and batch-mode users.
 - Protocol Requirements: Real-time protocols (e.g., MQTT, WebSockets, push APIs) will need to be supported and securely managed.
- **Recommendations:**
 - Engage pilots early to clarify time sensitivity of their data needs.
 - Develop a tiered data ingestion system:
 - Real-time ingestion layer for time-critical control.
 - Scheduled or batch ingestion for analytics/reporting.
 - Consider including a time synchronization framework (e.g., timestamps, latency logging) to ensure data coherence across partners.
- **Conclusions:**

This question reveals the hybrid nature of the U2Demo ecosystem, where some partners rely on real-time exchange for decision-making while others operate asynchronously. The platform should be flexible enough to support both.

Analysis of Question 22: What cybersecurity measures are currently in place in your systems? (Encryption, access management, data security, etc.)?

- **Key Observations:**
 - Watt-Is and NEW report the most comprehensive cybersecurity frameworks, implementing encryption, secure authentication, role-based access control (RBAC), and intrusion detection/prevention systems (IDPS). Watt-Is additionally conducts

regular security audits, indicating a proactive approach to threat monitoring and compliance.

- DHAAG has implemented the core measures: encryption, secure authentication, and RBAC, aligning well with baseline security expectations.
- INESC and EnGreen explicitly indicated no cybersecurity measures nor infrastructure in place.

- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**

- There is a significant disparity in cybersecurity maturity across partners, which poses a challenge for consistent risk management and trust-based data exchange within the U2Demo platform.
- The lack of basic measures (e.g., encryption, authentication) in some participants may hinder secure interoperability and increase exposure to threats in scenarios involving distributed P2P transactions.
- Stronger partners like NEW and Watt-Is can serve as benchmarks, but weaker configurations may limit the platform's ability to demonstrate end-to-end security compliance, especially under EU data protection regulations.

- **Recommendations:**

- Minimum cybersecurity requirements (e.g., TLS encryption, RBAC, and multi-factor authentication) should be defined and enforced across all participants before any integration with the U2Demo environment.
- A cybersecurity onboarding process should be established for partners lacking baseline controls, including technical support and compliance checklists.
- Consider implementing a risk-based tiering system, where partners with low cybersecurity readiness are assigned restricted roles or non-critical integration pathways during initial phases.
- Encourage regular security audits and documentation practices for all entities, especially those with current gaps.

- **Conclusions:**

- This question revealed critical inconsistencies in cybersecurity readiness across the consortium. While several partners are aligned with good practices, the absence of fundamental safeguards in others highlights the urgent need for baseline harmonisation to ensure secure and compliant operation of the U2Demo platform.

Analysis of Question 23: What encryption techniques are used for data at rest and in transit?

- **Key Observations:**

- Watt-Is provided the most complete and technically specific answer, using AES-256 for data at rest and TLS 1.3 for data in transit, both considered strong, industry-standard practices.
- DHAAG supports TLS 1.2 and 1.3, indicating encryption for data in transit but no mention of encryption for data at rest.
- KLIMAAN mentioned SFTP, which suggests encrypted transfer protocols are in use, but explicitly noted “None” for data at rest.
- EnGreen, INESC, and NEW show either no encryption or lack of awareness of what is currently in place.

- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**

- Encryption practices vary across partners, with some uncertainty regarding the use of encryption at rest. While this does not currently pose an operational issue, ensuring consistent application of encryption measures would help strengthen data confidentiality, integrity, and compliance in U2Demo’s cross-organisational data-sharing environment.
- Without standard encryption practices, particularly for data at rest, sensitive information exchanged between components or stored on local nodes could become a vulnerability point.

- **Recommendations:**

- Establish mandatory minimum encryption standards for U2Demo-related data flows:
 - At rest: AES-256 or equivalent;
 - In transit: TLS 1.2+, with TLS 1.3 as preferred.
- Partners should perform internal security audits to identify and address unknown or undocumented encryption configurations.
- Provide a technical reference guide on encryption practices to harmonise implementations across the consortium.
- Support low-readiness partners in adopting SFTP, TLS, and encryption-at-rest solutions through shared tools or templates.

- **Conclusions:**

- Responses to this question highlight a fragmented encryption landscape, with only one partner meeting high standards and several either lacking encryption or unaware of

their practices. To support secure, interoperable data exchange in U2Demo platform, establishing clear and enforceable encryption requirements will be essential.

Analysis of Question 24: What are the main cybersecurity risks you perceive in a P2P energy sharing platform? And data privacy related risks?

- **Key Observations:**

- EnGreen, NEW, and DHAAG provided detailed, risk-aware responses, highlighting both technical and data protection concerns.
- EnGreen noted threats from network intrusions, IoT vulnerabilities, and personal data exposure due to real-time usage patterns, aligning closely with the threat landscape of decentralized systems.
- DHAAG focused on the CIA triad (Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability), emphasizing control signal injection and system availability risks (e.g., fail-safes during connectivity loss). It also clarified that their use case does not involve personal data but acknowledged consumption-related risks.
- NEW detailed a broad spectrum of threats including data integrity (tampering or fake transactions), unauthorized access to algorithms, man-in-the-middle (MitM) attacks, and privacy risks tied to prosumer anonymity.
- Watt-IS flagged scalability as a key risk, linking increased participation with rising exposure to data misuse and manipulation.

- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**

- The responses underline that trust in a P2P platform relies heavily on robust cybersecurity and data protection mechanisms, especially in a system handling real-time, prosumer-level data and distributed control logic.
- Attack surfaces multiply with decentralisation (IoT devices, APIs, multiple actors), and several partners show a clear understanding of this, particularly around data integrity and privacy risks.
- The varying level of specificity suggests that not all participants may have conducted structured threat modelling, which could lead to unaddressed vulnerabilities during deployment or demonstration phases.
- Concerns about algorithmic security and transaction integrity are especially relevant in energy sharing use cases where value exchange is embedded.

- **Recommendations:**

- Conduct a threat and risk assessment specific to U2Demo P2P architecture.
- Require minimum baseline controls for device-level security (e.g., firmware integrity, secure boot), especially for smart meters and IoT interfaces.

- Define privacy-preserving mechanisms (e.g., pseudonymization⁸, differential privacy⁹) for prosumer related data.

- **Conclusions:**

- This question surfaced a nuanced view of cybersecurity and data privacy risks in a decentralized energy-sharing context. While some partners demonstrate strong awareness of threats to data integrity, privacy, and system availability, others appear less prepared or lack specificity. To build a secure and trustworthy U2Demo platform, the project should embed security and privacy by design, supported by a unified risk management framework across all participants.

Analysis of Question 25: What are the assets (software and/or hardware) you consider more critical in your demo regarding cybersecurity?

- **Key Observations:**

- Most respondents identified software assets (platforms, data, control systems) as the primary cybersecurity concern, while only a few explicitly mentioned hardware or physical components.
- EnGreen pointed to the Energy Management System (EMS) and data monitoring platforms (dashboards, APIs, databases) as potentially critical, acknowledging limited internal cybersecurity expertise.
- DHAAG focused on controllable hardware assets such as batteries, PV inverters, EV chargers, and circuit breakers—recognising their vulnerability to remote manipulation and physical consequences.
- NEW emphasized user data and core software, particularly data related to energy transactions and system behaviour, suggesting a data-centric security focus.
- INESC broadly identified the cloud-based platform as critical, without specifying which components or data types.
- Watt-Is noted that hardware responsibilities lie with external cloud providers, but stressed the importance of vulnerability management in their own software stack (OS packages, application dependencies), indicating a shared responsibility model.

⁸ Pseudonymization involves replacing identifying information (like names, social security numbers) with placeholder values or pseudonyms. The original data can still be linked to the individual if the "additional information" (e.g., the key to decrypt the pseudonym) is available and kept separately.

⁹ Differential privacy is a mathematically rigorous framework that aims to protect the privacy of individuals in a dataset when data analysis is performed. It involves adding controlled random noise to query results to mask individual contributions while still allowing for accurate aggregate statistics.

- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**

- The mix of asset types (from cloud platforms and EMS software to IoT field devices) reflects the heterogeneous attack surface of the U2Demo platform/environment.
- Control software and data management platforms appear as critical points of risk, particularly if they serve as central orchestration layers or host sensitive transactional data.
- Controllable field assets (as highlighted by DHAAG) bring additional risk due to the physical consequences of cyberattacks, such as forced disconnections, unsafe charging behaviour, or grid imbalance.
- The reliance on third-party infrastructure (as with Watt-Is and INESC) introduces supply chain risks and potential visibility gaps in asset-level security.

- **Recommendations:**

- Conduct a asset inventory per partner, categorising hardware and software based on potential impact in case of compromise.
- Prioritise cybersecurity controls around EMS platforms, transactional data pipelines, APIs, and control interfaces as these are core to platform operation and participant trust.
- Define security baselines and monitoring requirements for both internally managed and outsourced assets (especially cloud-managed infrastructure).
- Develop mitigation and isolation strategies for critical physical assets to prevent cascading failures in case of intrusion.

- **Conclusions:**

- Responses point to a varied landscape of critical assets across the U2Demo pilots, as spanning cloud services, software control layers, user data, and physical equipment. To ensure platform-wide resilience, U2Demo should implement a consistent approach to identifying and protecting critical assets.

Analysis of Question 26: What are the main cybersecurity threats you have identified in similar projects?

- **Key Observations:**

- Watt-Is provided the most comprehensive and technically grounded answer, referencing specific and common cybersecurity threats: web application vulnerabilities, phishing, brute-force attacks, and third-party certificate issues. This indicates an operational awareness of real-world security exposures in digital service environments.
- DHAAG highlighted a mix of physical and network-based threats, including unauthorised access to networked devices, use of household internet connections (less

secure), and publicly exposed portals, all of which are valid concerns in distributed energy environments.

- EnGreen viewed the project as an opportunity to improve cybersecurity competencies.
- NEW and INESC both reported no threats.

- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**

- The threats flagged by Watt-IS and DHAAG are directly relevant to U2Demo platform, especially in scenarios involving remote access, publicly available interfaces, and dependence on external partners or household infrastructure.

- **Recommendations:**

- Review exposure of public-facing interfaces and ensure controls like firewalls, VPNs, and hardened access protocols are in place, especially for EMS and portals.

- **Conclusions:**

- Only a subset of partners demonstrated awareness of cybersecurity threats from previous projects.

Analysis of Question 27: What data protection and user privacy practices have you implemented in your systems?

- **Key Observations:**

- Watt-Is presented a comprehensive and user-focused approach, incorporating informed consent, disclaimers on data use, and authorization/authentication mechanisms that ensure only data owners can access their data. This aligns well with GDPR principles of data minimization and purpose limitation.
- NEW applies anonymization of acquired data, a common and effective privacy-preserving method, though the implementation details are not specified.
- DHAAG reported the use of role-based access, which contributes to internal data protection but does not specifically address user-facing privacy measures or legal compliance mechanisms.
- EnGreen referred to the privacy policy of a third-party application provider (Huawei), implying reliance on external services for privacy compliance rather than an internal framework.
- INESC indicated that no user privacy practices are currently implemented.

- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**

- There is a wide variation in privacy readiness across partners. Some demonstrate alignment with GDPR-aligned practices (e.g., user control, data minimization), while

others appear to lack defined procedures or rely on external tools without internal accountability.

- The project may face challenges in ensuring uniform compliance with data protection regulations, especially given the potential processing of personal or household-level data in a P2P energy context.
- Lack of in-house policies or controls (as seen with INESC and EnGreen) may lead to non-compliance risks or difficulties during audits or data-sharing agreements.

- **Recommendations:**

- Establish a minimum privacy compliance checklist based on GDPR principles, including user consent, data access rights, purpose limitation, and storage duration.
- Partners should document and implement data handling policies for any personally identifiable information (PII) or household metadata involved in the pilot.
- Promote the adoption of data anonymization or pseudonymization techniques, especially when data is shared or stored outside direct user control.

- **Conclusions:**

- The responses reveal a mixed level of maturity in data protection and privacy practices across the consortium. While some partners have solid user control mechanisms and consent-based data handling, others lack internal procedures or defer responsibility to external providers. For U2Demo project to ensure legal compliance and participant trust, a harmonised and enforceable privacy framework should be adopted.

Analysis of Question 28: How do you handle identity verification and user authentication in your systems?

- **Key Observations:**

- NEW reports the use of Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) on its servers (a robust security measure aligned with best practices for critical infrastructure protection).
- Watt-IS supports a flexible authentication framework, enabling OAuth 2.0 integration (a widely accepted standard for secure delegated access), while still offering basic username-password login. This adaptability suggests readiness to interface with various identity providers.
- DHAAG notes that MFA is available via OpenRemote but not yet enabled, which implies technical capability exists but has not been operationalized (a potential gap in protection).
- EnGreen uses only account credentials, likely referring to a simple username-password combination without enhanced verification steps.

- INESC also relies on basic password-based authentication, which on its own may not be sufficient for securing sensitive user or system-level access in a P2P context.
- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**
- There is inconsistent implementation of secure authentication mechanisms across the consortium. Several partners lack strong identity verification methods, such as MFA or token-based authentication, which could undermine platform security.
- The absence of enforced MFA (or the reliance on default password authentication) may expose U2Demo project to account compromise risks, especially for interfaces handling transaction data, prosumer credentials, or control commands.
- While some partners (e.g., Watt-IS) are technically well-positioned to integrate secure identity services, others may require additional support or guidance to harden access controls.
- **Recommendations:**
- Define and adopt a common authentication baseline across U2Demo (at minimum, support for MFA and encrypted credential storage).
- Encourage the adoption of federated identity models (e.g., OAuth 2.0, SAML) to streamline secure access and reduce credential sprawl in a multi-partner environment.
- Ensure authentication practices are mapped to user roles and asset criticality, aligning verification levels with data/system sensitivity.
- **Conclusions:**
- This question highlights uneven adoption of secure authentication practices within the consortium. While some partners are equipped to implement or already use strong authentication protocols, others depend on basic credentials or have not activated available features. U2Demo platform must prioritise harmonised, secure access control mechanisms to protect user identity and system integrity.

Analysis of Question 29: How do you ensure compliance with GDPR or other data protection regulations in your country?

- **Key Observations:**
- Watt-Is offers the most comprehensive and structured approach to GDPR compliance. Their practices include purpose limitation, explicit consent, data minimisation, and clear terms and conditions, aligning well with key GDPR principles.
- DHAAG notes that they do not formally process personal data, but nevertheless aim to apply GDPR-equivalent standards.

- EnGreen relies on user acceptance of the app owner's privacy policy (likely third-party), indicating indirect compliance responsibility but no clear internal control or auditability mechanism.
- INESC claims compliance by “following GDPR rules”, but without detailing how this is operationalised, documented, or audited.
 - **Implications for U2Demo platform:**
- DHAAG’s voluntary alignment with GDPR despite not handling personal data shows a good example of precautionary compliance, which could be used to guide best practices across the consortium.
 - **Recommendations:**
 - Recommended that all partners to document how they implement the core GDPR principles: data minimisation, purpose limitation, transparency, consent, and data subject rights.
 - A U2Demo-wide data protection policy should be adopted, including shared templates for privacy notices, data subject consent forms, and procedures for breach notification.
 - **Conclusions:**
 - While one partner demonstrates strong alignment with GDPR, others provide limited or externalised approaches. For U2Demo project to ensure consistent regulatory compliance and protect data subjects' rights, a shared and transparent privacy governance framework can be adopted and uniformly enforced across all participants.

Analysis of Question 30: Have you worked with confidential computing technologies before? (If yes, what tools and approaches have you used?)

- **Key Observations:**
 - Five out of six respondents (EnGreen, DHAAG, KLIMAAN, INESC, and Watt-IS) reported no prior experience with confidential computing technologies, but expressed a clear interest in exploring them.
 - EDP NEW was the only partner to state that they do not see a need for confidential computing, indicating a lack of perceived relevance for their current or planned architecture.
 - The absence of prior exposure is consistent across both technical and implementation-focused partners.
- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**
 - However, the strong interest in exploration from most partners creates a valuable opening to introduce these technologies gradually, especially in sensitive P2P data-sharing contexts.

- The lack of perceived need from NEW may reflect a focus on conventional data security methods or a preference for system-level protections rather than application-layer cryptographic safeguards.
- **Recommendations:**
- Identify specific use cases within U2Demo (e.g., secure aggregation of peer transactions, privacy-preserving settlement calculations) where these technologies could demonstrate tangible value.
- **Conclusions:**
- Most partners have not yet worked with confidential computing but are open to exploring its potential. The project will validate a valuable opportunity to introduce and test emerging privacy-enhancing technologies in a structured and low-risk way, particularly where data sensitivity or regulatory compliance justifies their use.

Analysis of Question 31: How is data securely exchanged between energy producers, consumers, and grid operators?

- **Key Observations:**
- Watt-Is provided the most thorough and technically specific response, referencing the use of TLS, SFTP, HTTPS, and AES-256 to secure data both in transit and at rest, with attention to integrity and confidentiality.
- NEW also mentioned secure communication channels, including the use of dedicated digital platforms and secure sFTP, indicating structured methods for controlled data exchange.
- DHAAG gave a brief but clear response (“end-to-end encryption”) which suggests an understanding of the importance of protecting data across its entire transmission path.
- EnGreen stated that no real-time data exchange occurs in their energy community. They currently rely on aggregated data provided semi-annually by the GSE (Gestore Servizi Energetici) but expressed interest in understanding best practices for future secure data exchanges.
- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**
- The responses indicate a solid awareness among several partners of the need for encryption and secure transfer protocols. This is encouraging for the design of interoperable and secure data flows across the U2Demo platform.
- However, the absence of real-time data exchange in EnGreen’s current setup suggests potential challenges in integrating them into U2Demo’s expected operational model, where near real-time interaction between stakeholders may be required.
- **Recommendations:**

- Define a standardised set of secure communication protocols (e.g., TLS 1.3, HTTPS, SFTP) for all data exchanges within the U2Demo platform, along with encryption benchmarks (e.g., AES-256).
- Ensure end-to-end encryption not only in transport but also in application-level interfaces, APIs, and control signals between systems.
- Identify and document data exchange roles and responsibilities, especially in use cases involving multi-party sharing across pilots and third-party platforms.
- **Conclusions:**
- Most partners demonstrate a good level of awareness and application of secure data exchange mechanisms. While some already employ robust encryption protocols and dedicated platforms, others are still in exploratory phases. To ensure consistent and secure interoperability across U2Demo, common standards and practical implementation support should be provided.

Analysis of Question 32: What protocols are used for secure communication?

- **Key Observations:**
- Watt-Is and DHAAG demonstrated the most advanced use of secure communication protocols, with Watt-IS specifying TLS 1.3 for HTTP-based communication and SFTP for file transfers, and DHAAG listing a broader range including HTTPS, MQTTS, and TLS 1.2/1.3.
- NEW also indicated the use of TLS/SSL for HTTP traffic and sFTP for secure file transfers, showing basic but appropriate coverage.
- INESC reported no secure communication protocols in use, which presents a potential security gap, especially in scenarios involving data or control exchanges.
- EnGreen acknowledged that they currently use no secure protocols, but expressed an interest in learning more.
- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**
- While some partners use industry-standard protocols (TLS 1.2/1.3, HTTPS, SFTP), others are still operating with no secure communication layers, which could pose risks to data confidentiality, integrity, and system trust.
- Protocols like MQTTS, as noted by DHAAG, are especially relevant for IoT and edge-device communication and may be of growing importance as U2Demo solutions scales or decentralises further.
- **Recommendations:**
- Define protocol baseline for secure communication across U2Demo.

- Include secure protocol validation in platform-level integration tests and pre-deployment checks.
- **Conclusions:**
- Secure communication protocols are in place for several partners, notably Watt-IS, DHAAG, and NEW, but are absent for others. U2Demo project must address these inconsistencies by enforcing a baseline protocol framework and supporting less mature partners in upgrading their systems to meet common security standards.

Analysis of Question 33: Are smart contracts used for managing energy transactions? If so, have they been audited?

- **Key Observations:**
- Five respondents (EnGreen, DHAAG, NEW, INESC, and Watt-Is) confirmed that smart contracts are not currently being used to manage energy transactions in their systems.
- Watt-Is explicitly stated they are not relying on Web3 technologies, clarifying a deliberate design choice rather than a capability gap.
- EnGreen expressed interest in learning more about smart contracts, suggesting openness to future exploration despite lack of implementation.
- No partners reported experience with auditing smart contracts, indicating that this capability is not yet part of the consortium's cybersecurity or blockchain readiness.
- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**
- The complete absence of smart contracts in current implementations reflects a conservative or traditional approach to transaction management among partners.
- This could limit experimentation with decentralised energy governance or automated settlement mechanisms, which are often cited as use cases for blockchain and smart contract technologies in P2P energy sharing.
- On the other hand, not using smart contracts avoids risks related to immature implementations, poor auditability, and regulatory ambiguity (known challenges in the Web3 space).
- **Conclusions:**
- No partners currently employ smart contracts in energy transaction workflows, though one expressed curiosity about future possibilities.

Analysis of Question 34: What authentication mechanisms are in place?

- **Key Observations:**
- Watt-Is provided the most robust and detailed response, implementing both OAuth2 client credentials flow (for system-to-system authentication) and authorization code

flow (for user delegation), which are industry-standard and secure methods for managing authenticated access.

- DHAAG also uses OAuth 2.0, demonstrating good alignment with best practices for secure access management, particularly in web and API-based systems.
- KLIMAAN implements PKI (Public Key Infrastructure) and fixed IP restrictions, which together offer strong authentication and network-layer access control, especially suitable for constrained or embedded environments.
- INESC and EnGreen reported having no authentication mechanisms, presenting a major vulnerability in contexts where user or system identities must be verified to protect access to data, devices, or transactions.
- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**
- Partners with strong implementations (Watt-IS, DHAAG, KLIMAAN) provide examples that could help standardise identity and access management practices.
- The absence of authentication at some sites may hinder the secure integration of APIs, dashboards, or user-facing services into the broader U2Demo platform/architecture.
- **Recommendations:**
- Define and enforce a minimum authentication requirement across U2Demo partners, such as OAuth2 or equivalent token-based systems.
- Provide lightweight identity management solutions or shared modules for partners lacking authentication, especially for access to critical services or user interfaces.
- Promote the use of multi-factor authentication where feasible, and ensure secure storage and handling of credentials.
- **Conclusions:**
- Authentication practices vary widely across the consortium. While several partners apply modern, secure methods, others currently operate with no authentication controls. To ensure secure system integration and protect user and operational data, U2Demo project must establish common authentication standards and provide support for partners who have yet to implement them.

Analysis of Question 35: Is there a plan for incident response in case of a cybersecurity breach?

- **Key Observations:**
- Watt-Is is the only respondent with a formal and recent Cybersecurity Incident Response Policy, indicating proactive planning and a structured approach to handling potential security breaches.

- EnGreen, INESC, and DHAAG all reported having no current plan in place, while KLIMAAN acknowledged that such a plan still needs to be developed.
- Overall, five out of six partners either lack an incident response plan or are in early stages of considering one.
- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**
- In a multi-party platform involving sensitive energy and user data, even a minor breach from one node could have cascading effects, making shared preparedness essential.
- Watt-IS's policy could serve as a useful reference model for other partners.
- **Recommendations:**
- Having a central incident coordination protocol for the U2Demo platform, might be a nice to have.
- **Conclusions:**
- The vast majority of partners currently lack a cybersecurity incident response plan, with only one entity having a documented policy. This gap must be addressed to ensure that U2Demo platform can detect, respond to, and recover from potential security breaches in a coordinated and compliant manner.

Analysis of Question 36: What mechanisms are in place to ensure regulatory reporting and auditing?

- **Key Observations:**
- Watt-Is demonstrates a partial approach to auditing, using Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) and Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC), and logging user interactions via the user interface. While this does not constitute a full auditing system, it reflects a degree of traceability and accountability for data access and user activity.
- DHAAG performs periodic penetration testing (PEN testing) aligned with the PTES (Penetration Testing Execution Standard), which supports compliance and security assurance, though it focuses more on vulnerability exposure than regulatory reporting.
- KLIMAAN states they are required to comply with GDPR, but provides no evidence of supporting mechanisms like data access logs, audit trails, or compliance dashboards.
- EnGreen and INESC report having no mechanisms in place to support regulatory reporting or system-level auditing.
- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**

- There is a lack of formalised auditing frameworks and compliance with relevant regulations (e.g., GDPR, NIS2¹⁰), across most partners.
- The absence of standardised logging or audit readiness could hinder cross-partner accountability within the U2Demo platform, especially if sensitive or personal data is exchanged.
- **Conclusions:**
- To support compliance, transparency, and trust within U2Demo platform, unified audit and reporting practices must be introduced and scaled consistently.

Analysis of Question 37: Are payment transactions secured using blockchain or the traditional financial system?

- **Key Observations:**
- EnGreen is the only partner explicitly using the traditional financial system to handle payment transactions, implying reliance on established banking infrastructure.
- Watt-IS, KLIMAAN, INESC, and NEW all confirmed that blockchain technologies are not in use..
- DHAAG noted that there are no automated payment transactions involved in their setup, suggesting that financial exchanges are either manual or out of scope for their participation.
- Across all respondents, there is a clear absence of blockchain-based payment mechanisms, and no indication that any partners are experimenting with token-based or decentralised finance approaches.
- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**
- The consistent reliance on traditional or non-automated financial systems suggests a cautious approach to the handling of value exchange, prioritising stability and regulatory compliance over innovation in financial technologies.
- While this reduces complexity and avoids the risks associated with smart contracts or crypto assets, it also means that automated or decentralised settlement mechanisms (which are often discussed in the context of P2P energy trading) are not currently being explored.
- **Recommendations:**

¹⁰ Directive (EU) 2022/2555

- If financial settlement becomes a demonstrable component of any pilot, ensure that interfaces with traditional financial systems (e.g., SEPA, APIs) are secure, auditable, and aligned with EU payment regulations.

- **Conclusions:**

- All partners either rely on the traditional financial system or do not engage in payment transactions at all. Blockchain is not currently applied to financial flows, with its role in U2Demo focused mainly on supporting the energy sharing algorithms.

Analysis of Question 38: Is there a dispute resolution mechanism for incorrect or malicious energy transactions?

- **Key Observations:**

- None of the six respondents currently have a dispute resolution mechanism in place for incorrect or malicious energy transactions.
- Watt-IS provided contextual justification, stating that P2P transactions are not currently permitted under Portuguese regulation, and therefore no dispute system has been developed. This reflects a legal and regulatory constraint rather than a lack of technical readiness.
- DHAAG and KLIMAAN acknowledged that mechanisms are not yet implemented, suggesting that the issue is on their radar but has not been prioritised or developed.
- EnGreen, INESC, and EDP NEW reported a complete absence of dispute resolution mechanisms.

- **Implications for U2Demo platform:**

- No implications from the answers.

- **Recommendations:**

- Integrate transaction logging and auditability features to support dispute investigations and traceability, including time-stamping, signature verification, and energy flow validation.

- **Conclusions:**

- None of the U2Demo partners currently have dispute resolution mechanisms in place for energy transactions. While this is partially attributable to regulatory limitations, the absence of planning or proposed frameworks represents a potential barrier to future deployment. Introducing dispute-handling capabilities will be critical for enabling secure, accountable, and user-trusted energy sharing environments.

Analysis of Question 39: Do you have security measures against rogue nodes injecting false data into the system?

➤ **Key Observations:**

- Only DHAAG reported having an explicit security measure in place: new nodes can only be added with admin permission and password protection. This demonstrates a control barrier at the onboarding stage.
- Watt-IS again framed its response in the context of regulatory constraints in Portugal, noting that P2P transactions are not active yet. However, they also indicated readiness and willingness to implement protections when necessary.
- EnGreen, KLIMAAN, INESC, and NEW acknowledged either no protections, lack of awareness, or absence of planning. This reveals a general underestimation of the threat posed by rogue nodes (a serious risk in decentralized or semi-decentralized energy platforms).

➤ **Implications for U2Demo platform:**

- Without verification protocols and behavioral checks on participating nodes, the platform is at risk of propagating corrupted data, inflated readings, or manipulated market signals.
- The absence of such mechanisms also jeopardizes regulatory compliance, auditability, and confidence in settlement processes, particularly for markets that will rely on automated metering and digital communication.

➤ **Recommendations:**

- Introduce node attestation procedures to ensure only trusted devices interact with the system.
- Design data validation pipelines that check for anomalies, inconsistencies, or malicious patterns in device-submitted information.

➤ **Conclusions:**

- Most partners currently lack mechanisms to protect against rogue nodes injecting false data. While regulatory limitations are a valid constraint in some cases, proactive security planning is essential for future P2P deployment and to uphold data trustworthiness. Basic access controls, coupled with validation and attestation strategies, can be developed and tested as part of the platform's cybersecurity framework.

Analysis of Question 40: Do you foresee any challenges in implementing confidential computing in your system?

➤ **Key Observations:**

- EnGreen identified hardware compatibility as a potential challenge, specifically with existing IoT and edge devices, which may not support the secure enclaves or trusted execution environments required for confidential computing.

- DHAAG acknowledged a lack of knowledge as a barrier, indicating that internal expertise and awareness are still developing in this area.
- Watt-Is showed confidence in the feasibility of implementing confidential computing, noting that it could be addressed via managed services from cloud providers (e.g., Microsoft Azure), which simplifies integration for non-specialist teams.
 - **Implications for U2Demo platform:**
 - No implications to the U2Demo platform
 - **Recommendations:**
 - Conduct a feasibility assessment to identify where in the U2Demo architecture such technologies would be most impactful and easiest to integrate, starting with back-end services before edge-level deployment.
 - **Conclusions:**
 - The integration of confidential computing is viewed with uncertainty or caution by most respondent partners. While the potential is acknowledged, concerns range from technical compatibility to knowledge gaps. This indicates a need for targeted guidance and incremental integration pathways within U2Demo to support eventual adoption.

Analysis of Question 41: Do you have any additional suggestions or concerns regarding standards, cybersecurity, or the integration of the U2Demo platform?

- Only KLIMAAN provided a response, highlighting two specific requirements:
 - The need for a GDPR-compliant data sharing agreement to ensure lawful processing of personal or sensitive data accessed via U2Demo.
 - The requirement for a fixed IP address and public key to securely enable data access from the Fluvius data source, indicating an intent to restrict and authenticate access endpoints.
- The points raised reflect broader concerns likely shared across the U2Demo partners regarding legal clarity and secure interoperability. Proactively addressing these elements will support smoother platform integration and foster trust in cross-partner data exchange mechanisms.

10 APPENDIX C: BOs list

Business Object
House Resources Scheduling <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EC Member ID - Time stamp - Time series for the next 24 hours in 15 minute intervals: - Forecasts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PV production - Consumption profile - Aggregated injection of the other EC members - Energy price - Schedule: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - BESS: SOC in % - Heat Pump: On/Off (only IT pilot) - CS: charging profile (only IT pilot)
Rescheduling Decision
Invoice with incentives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EC ID - Time stamp - Measurements received from the DSO - Incentive - Whole incentive
Invoice for EC Member <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EC Member ID - Time stamp - Measurements of the DSO (time series per 15 minutes for the month of consumption and injection) - Price over this time - Total amount to pay - Total remuneration for injecting energy to the grid - Total bill
Forecast (only in the BE pilot) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Member ID - Time Stamp - Time series for the next 24 hours in 15 min steps, content varies according to the type of member: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forecasts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PV production (in kWh) (members with PV panels) - Own consumption (in kWh) (members with PV panels) - Injection of the EC members with PV panels (members without PV panels) - Grid price of the energy (in €/kWh)
Monitoring data for EC members with PV (only BE pilot) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC member - Time stamp - PV production - Consumption of this EC member - Injection data of this EC member - Injection of the whole EC

Monitoring data for EC members without PV (only BE pilot) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC member - Time stamp - Consumption of this EC member - Injection of the whole EC
Invoice for grid consumption of EC Member with PV (only BE pilot) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC Member - Time Stamp - Time series for the whole month in 15 min intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consumption (kWh) - Energy price (€/kWh) - Total amount to pay (€)
Consumption data of EC Member with PV (only BE pilot) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC Member - Time series for the whole month in 15 min intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consumption (kWh)
Amount of shared energy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC Member - Time series for the whole month in 15 min intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Amount of energy consumed through the EC (kWh)
Invoice preliminary information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC member (IT and BE pilots)/ ID of the EC (NL pilot) - Time stamp - Consumption information (Timeseries for the whole month with 15 min intervals) - Injection information (Timeseries for the whole month in 15 min intervals) - Consumption updated (kWh) (Timeseries for the whole month in 15 min intervals) (PT Pilot)
Credit Points <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of EC Member - Time stamp - Time series for the whole month in 15 min. intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Credit points
Self-consumption invoice for all EC Members <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC Members - Time stamp - Time series of the whole month in 15 min. intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-consumption of all members (kWh) - Price per unit of self-consumption (€/kWh) - Total amount to pay (€)
Self-consumption data of each member with PV (only BE pilot) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC member - Time stamp - Time series for the whole month in 15 min. intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-consumption of this member
Self-consumption invoice (only BE pilot) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC member - Time stamp - Time series of the whole month in 15 min. intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-consumption (kWh) - Price per unit of self-consumption (€/kWh) - Total amount to pay (€)

Invoice for grid consumption of EC member without PV

- ID of the EC Member
- Time Stamp
- Time series for the whole month in 15 mins. intervals:
 - Consumption (kWh)
 - Credit points
 - Energy price (€/kWh)
- Total amount to pay (€)

Invoice for shared energy through the EC

- ID of the EC Member
- Time Stamp
- Time series of the whole month in 15 min. intervals:
 - Consumption (kWh)
 - Energy price (€/kWh)
- Total amount to pay (€)

House Measurements

- Member ID
 - Time stamp
 - PV data (except for members without PV in BE pilot):
 - S_AC (VA)
 - S_AC_L1 (VA)
 - S_AC_L2 (VA)
 - S_AC_L3 (VA)
 - P_AC (W)
 - P_AC_L1 (W)
 - P_AC_L2 (W)
 - P_AC_L3 (W)
 - Q_AC (VAr)
 - Q_AC_L1 (VAr)
 - Q_AC_L2 (VAr)
 - Q_AC_L3 (VAr)
 - PF_L1 (Real)
 - PF_L2 (Real)
 - PF_L3 (Real)
 - U_AC_L1 (V)
 - U_AC_L2 (V)
 - U_AC_L3 (V)
 - I_AC_L1 (A)
 - I_AC_L2 (A)
 - I_AC_L3 (A)
 - Ump_DC_St1 (V)
 - Imp_DC_St1 (A)
 - P_DC_St1 (W)
 - Ump_DC_St2 (V)
 - Imp_DC_St2 (A)
 - P_DC_St2 (W)
 - P_DC (W)
 - f (Hz)
 - Temperature (°C)
 - Inverter State (Integer)
 - House data:
 - S_Imp (VA)
-

S_Imp_L1 (VA)
S_Imp_L2 (VA)
S_Imp_L3 (VA)
S_Exp (VA)
S_Exp_L1 (VA)
S_Exp_L2 (VA)
S_Exp_L3 (VA)
P_Imp (W)
P_Imp_L1 (W)
P_Imp_L2 (W)
P_Imp_L3 (W)
P_Exp (W)
P_Exp_L1 (W)
P_Exp_L2 (W)
P_Exp_L3 (W)
Q_Imp (VAr)
Q_Imp_L1 (VAr)
Q_Imp_L2 (VAr)
Q_Imp_L3 (VAr)
Q_Exp (VAr)
Q_Exp_L1 (VAr)
Q_Exp_L2 (VAr)
Q_Exp_L3 (VAr)
PF_L1 (Real)
PF_L2 (Real)
PF_L3 (Real)
U_L1 (V)
U_L2 (V)
U_L3 (V)
I_L1 (A)
I_L2 (A)
I_L3 (A)
f (Hz)

- **Storage data:**

SOC (%)
Temperature (°C)
S_Imp (VA)
S_Imp_L1 (VA)
S_Imp_L2 (VA)
S_Imp_L3 (VA)
S_Exp (VA)
S_Exp_L1 (VA)
S_Exp_L2 (VA)
S_Exp_L3 (VA)
P_Imp (W)
P_Imp_L1 (W)
P_Imp_L2 (W)
P_Imp_L3 (W)
P_Exp (W)
P_Exp_L1 (W)
P_Exp_L2 (W)
P_Exp_L3 (W)

Q_Imp (VAr)
Q_Imp_L1 (VAr)
Q_Imp_L2 (VAr)
Q_Imp_L3 (VAr)
Q_Exp (VAr)
Q_Exp_L1 (VAr)
Q_Exp_L2 (VAr)
Q_Exp_L3 (VAr)
PF_L1 (Real)
PF_L2 (Real)
PF_L3 (Real)
U_L1 (V)
U_L2 (V)
U_L3 (V)
I_L1 (A)
I_L2 (A)
I_L3 (A)
f (Hz)

- Possibly states of additional flexible assets (such as Heat pumps in IT pilot, CS in IT pilot)
- Possibly injection data of the other members of the EC

Answer to flexibility request

- Yes/no

Flexibility request

- Amount of requested flexibility
- Starting time of this flexibility
- Renumeration for the flexibility (only NL pilot)
- Duration of the flexibility

EC internal energy prices

- Time stamp
- Time series for the day in 15 min intervals:
 - Grid buy price (including transmission fees and taxes)
 - Grid sell price (including transmission fees and taxes)
 - Internal price of the energy community

Scheduling information of a HEMS

- ID of the HEMS
- Time stamp
- Time series for the day in 15 min intervals:
 - Import of this EC Member
 - Export of this EC Member
- Available flexibility (up/down, amount, time interval)

EC member Imp/Exp Scheduling

- ID of the HEMS
- Time stamp
- Time series for the day in 15 min intervals:
 - Power imported to this EC Member
 - Power exported from this EC Member

Forecast information for one HEMS

- ID of the HEMS
- Time stamp
- Time series for the day in 15 min intervals:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PV production forecast - Consumption forecast
Forecast information for the GEMS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time stamp - Time series for the day in 15 min intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PV production forecast of the whole EC - Consumption forecast of the whole EC
DA profile <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC - Time Stamp - Time series for the day in 15 min intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consumption of the EC - Injection of the EC
T-prognosis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC - Time Stamp - Time series for the day in 15 min intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consumption of the EC - Injection of the EC
Flexibility profile <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC - Time stamp - Flex offers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possible flexibility (start time, duration, amount, up/down) - Requested price for this flexibility
Setpoints and incentives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the HEMS - Setpoint for import/export value of this HEMS - Incentive for the HEMS to meet these setpoints
Community measurements <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC - Time stamp - Data of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - consumption of the whole EC - Production of the whole EC - Injection of the whole EC - Price inside the community (only NL pilot) - Grid energy price
Invoice from Supplier <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC - Time Stamp - Time series of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consumption data (kWh) - Injection data (kWh) - Price for consumption (€/kWh) - Renumeration for injection (€/kWh) - Total amount to pay/amount of remuneration (€)
Invoice from DSO <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC - Time stamp - Fixed cost for the whole month for the connection to the grid

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cost for the whole month for the contracted capacity - Cost for the whole month for the amount of kWh used in the respective month - Cost for the whole month for the maximum power (15 min average) in that month - Total amount to pay
Invoice from the measurement company <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC - Time stamp - Bill for the EC
Invoice for EC member <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ID of the EC Member - Time stamp - Information on the invoice of the Retailer - Time series of the data of this EC Member: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consumption data - Injection data - Time series of the EC internal energy price - Total amount to pay/of remuneration
Metering data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EC Member ID - Time series of the whole month in 15 min intervals <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consumption (kWh) - Production (kWh)
Energy sharing information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EC Member ID - Sharing coefficients for each EC member (% and kWh) -
Grid fee information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grid fee for the total energy shared (€)
Invoice grid fee <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EC Member ID (who participated in energy sharing) - Participation in energy sharing (% and kWh) - Total amount to pay for grid usage (€)
Electricity price information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time stamp - Time series for the day in 15 min intervals: - Retailer price (€/kWh) - Internal EC price (€/kWh) (NL and PT pilot)
Offers and bids information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EC Member ID - Time Stamp - Time series for the day in 15 min intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offer ID - Offer quantity (kWh) - Offer price (€/kWh) - Bid ID - Bid quantity (kWh) - Bid price (€/kWh)
Energy Sharing Market Clearing Results <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EC Member ID - Time Stamp

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time series for the day in 15 min intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offer quantity cleared (kWh) - Offer price cleared (€/kWh) - Bid quantity cleared (kWh) - Bid price cleared (€/kWh) - Total amount to pay (€) - Total amount to be remunerated (€)
Aggregated offers and bids information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EC Member ID - Time Stamp - Time series for the day in 15 min intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offer ID - Offer quantity (kWh) - Offer price (€/kWh) - Bid ID - Bid quantity (kWh) - Bid price (€/kWh)
Matching information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EC Member ID - Time Stamp - Offer(s) ID selected - Bid(s) ID selected
Offers and bids matched Information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EC Member ID • Time Stamp • Time series for the day in 15 min intervals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Offer ID ○ Offer quantity (kWh) ○ Offer price (€/kWh) ○ Bid ID ○ Bid quantity (kWh) ○ Bid price (€/kWh)
Payment production preliminary Information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EC Member ID • Time series of the whole month in 15 min intervals <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Production updated (kWh)
Payment production Information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EC Member ID • Time series of the whole month in 15 min intervals <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Production updated (kWh) • Total amount to be remunerated (€)
Invoice for energy transactions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EC Member ID (who participated in energy transactions) • Participation in energy sharing (% and kWh) • Consumption price through energy transacted(€/kWh) • Total amount to pay (€)
Payment for energy shared <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EC Member ID • Total amount to pay (€)
Exchange information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total amount to buy vouchers (€)

Vouchers information

- vouchers (€)

Flexibility request information :

- Flexibility Request ID
- Flexibility Zone ID
- Service Type (e.g. Secure)
- Flexibility Direction (Reduce/Increase Consumption and Reduce/Increase Generation)
- Service Window (start-time timestamp, end-time timestamp)
- Utilization fee (€/MWh)
- Availability fee (€/MW/h)
- Maximum runtime (min)
- Response time (min)
- Service recovery time (min)

Aggregated flexibility requests list:

- List of flexibility requests published in PICLO

Response to flexibility request

- Flexibility Request ID
- EC ID
- Maximum runtime (min)
- Response time (min)
- Service recovery time (min)
- Reference value (MW)
- Bid on flexible power (MW)
- Bid on utilization fee (€/MWh)
- Bid on availability fee (€/MW/h)

Flexibility Market Clearing Results

- Flexibility Request ID
- List of EC IDs for the flexibility request cleared
 - EC ID
 - Flexible power cleared (MW)
 - Utilization fee cleared (€/MWh)
 - Availability fee cleared (€/MW/h)

Validation of market results

- List of EC IDs validated
 - EC ID
 - Validation status (Passed, Failed, Passed with lower (updated) flexible power)
 - Validated flexible power (MW)

EC results Flexibility Market

- EC ID
 - Flexibility Request ID
 - Flexibility Zone ID
 - Service Type (Sustain, Restore, Dynamic or Secure)
 - Flexibility Direction (Reduce/Increase Consumption and Reduce/Increase Generation)
 - Service Window (start-time timestamp, end-time timestamp)
 - Validated flexible power (MW)
-

- Utilization fee cleared (€/MWh)
- Availability fee cleared (€/MW/h)
- Maximum runtime (min)
- Response time (min)
- Service recovery time (min)
- Reference value (MW)

EC manager Flexibility payment

- EC ID
- Availability payment computation:
 - Validated flexible power (MW)
 - Number of available hours (h)
 - Availability fee cleared (€/MW/h)
 - Total availability remuneration (€)
- Utilization payment computation
 - List of activation requests (start-time timestamp, end-time timestamp)
 - Total delivered flexibility (MWh)
 - Utilization fee cleared (€/MWh)
 - Total utilization remuneration (€)
- Total remuneration for flexibility (€)

EC member Flexibility payment

- EC member ID
- Total payment for flexibility in vouchers (€)
 - Member availability remuneration (€)
 - Member utilization remuneration (€)

Auction requirements:

- Request ID
- Elastic demands list: price (€/MWh) and quantity (MW)
- Inelastic demand list: quantity (MW)

Response to frequency auction

- Auction ID
- EC ID
- Direction (up/down)
- Maximum quantity (MW)
- Minimum quantity (MW)
- Price (€/MWh)
- Service window (Start-time timestamp, end-time timestamp)
- Bid on capacity (MW)
- Bid on reserve price (€/MW/15min)

Auction results

- Request ID
- Elastic demands cleared list: price cleared (€/MWh) and quantities (MW)
- Inelastic demands cleared list: quantity (MW)

EC results mFRR Market

- EC ID
- Auction ID
- Direction (up/down)

-
- **Quantity cleared (MW)**
 - **Price cleared (€/MWh)**
 - **Service window (Start-time timestamp, end-time timestamp)**
-

EC manager mFRR remuneration

- **EC ID**
 - **Energy remuneration:**
 - **List of activation events**
 - **Total activated energy (kWh)**
 - **Total energy remuneration (€)**
 - **Total remuneration for mFRR activation (€)**
-

EC member mFRR remuneration

- **EC member ID**
 - **Total payment for mFRR activations in vouchers (€)**
-